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The Analysis of Presupposition in George Orwell's Novella Animal Farm

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ABSTRACT

This research attempts to investigate the pragmatics presupposition in George Orwell's Novella Animal Farm. Specifically, it tries to identify and classify the presupposition used in conversation in Orwell's novella. The identification is based on the presupposition triggers and classification based on six type of presupposition. The research also attempts to analyze the function in the use of presupposition in conversation. The data in this research are in form of utterances containing presupposition. Based on the classification of six presupposition types according to Yule's theory (1996), 180 presuppositions are found: 69 (38,3%) existential triggered by definite description and possessive construction, 35 (19,4%) lexical triggered by change of state verb; implicative predicate; iterative, 53 (29,4%) structural triggered by WH-question, 4 (2,2%) factive triggered by factive verb/predicate aware & glad and 19 (10,6%) non-factive triggered by the verb dream & imagine. Based on the six language function by Jakobson (1960), there are 5 functions of presupposition in the novella which are, 57 (47, 9%) referential, 33(27,7%) emotive, 25(21,1%) conative, 3(2,5%) poetic and 1 (0,8%) phatic. In this research, the practice of referential function in applying presupposition is considered as the most

frequent.

Keywords: *Presupposition, presupposition triggers, Novella, George Orwell*

INTRODUCTION

In the effort of expressing thought and feeling, human being cannot communicate each other without the use of language. It makes everything surrounding us seems meaningful. The use of language in the perspective of what actually a speaker says to the hearer will have particular meaning if both parties know which utterance that is suitable in the context of the information emerges from the utterance and gets the understanding and influence of the context in which they are performed and it can be fully comprehended by the hearer. Language and context are supposed to be a basic to account speaker and hearer language understanding that refer to the utterances and speech events.

By this, the range of expression in the form of utterances from word, phrases, clauses to the full sentence construction and the use of it cannot be separated from the understanding of the context. Sometimes a speaker having an assumption that certain information had already known by the listener, even though the information are not appear directly in the speaker's sentence. It is not simple ways of catching and comprehending the given information. A Listener needs to highlight on the actual word's meaning and what the speaker's mean in the same context. In order to avoid the misinterpretation in meaning it will be greatly dealing with presupposition.

Presupposition is a thing that is presupposed, while presupposes means to assume something true before it is proved. Presupposition can occur in verbal and written language, in daily conversation or in the use of conversation in a novella. Novella is one of the genres of prose works which attract many readers. The uses of presupposition by the characters in novella should be appropriate so that the readers will understand it.

Based on the explanation above, the writer analysed the presupposition in George Orwell's Novella Animal Farm. There are two reasons why this study is worthwhile to be investigated. First, speaker need to understand about presupposition to help him produces utterances that easy to understand by listener. Speakers should produce the sentence that its presupposition understandable by the listener to avoid information gap and misinterpretation between speaker and listener. Second,, when the speaker delivers his message to the listener in unstated sentence, the listener cannot know and infer the meaning of speaker's utterance from the sentence itself, so it must be added with presuppositions in true context. Beside that the listener also needs to have adequate knowledge about presupposition to help him to catch the speaker's message. The use of presupposition is not only in daily life but also in literary works like novella.

Related to the phenomena above, there are many possible research problems that needs investigation, such as the types, uses and function of presupposition. Yule (2006: 116) stated a definition of presupposition that is what a speaker assumes is true or known by a listener.

In addition, presupposition plays an important role in the production and comprehension of speech act. It is defined from different points of view, each of which is similar to each other in some way or another. Hudson (2000: 321) states that "a presupposition" is something assumed (presupposed) to be true in a sentence which asserts other information".

In the following example, sentence (a) presupposes sentence (b).

1. a. The child sneezed again.

b. The child had sneezed before.

The first sentence presupposes the information in the second, and this is apparent in the fact that if the first sentence is negated, the truth of the second remains unchanged:

1. c. The child did not sneeze again.

Thus, the negation of the sentence can be considered as one of the tests used to check for the presupposition underlying the sentence, as in:

2. a. Mary's hat is red.

b. Mary's hat is not red.

Although these two sentences have opposite meanings, the underlying presupposition, 'Mary has a hat', remains true (the same). This case is called by linguists as "constancy under negation", which is one of the properties used in pragmatics for testing presuppositions.

Yule (2000: 27) sees that presupposition has been associated with the use of a large number of words, phrases, and structures. These linguistic forms are considered to be indicators of potential presupposition, which can only become actual presupposition in context with speakers. Thus, he states six types of presupposition which are: existential, factive, non-factive, lexical, structural and counterfactual. These six types of presupposition can be brought together under the heading of potential presupposition which represents the whole.

The existential presupposition is assumed to be present either in possessive constructions (such as: your car presupposes (») you have a car) or in any definite noun phrase as in using expressions like: the King of Sweden, the cat, etc. in which the speaker presupposes the existence of the entities or objects.

The second type of presupposition is called factive presupposition since some words are used in the sentences to denote facts, such as know, realize, regret, glad, odd and aware. For example, everybody knows that John is ill presupposes that John is ill.

The third type of presupposition is called non-factive presupposition, which is assumed not to be true. Verbs like dream, imagine and pretend are used with the presupposition that what follows is not true. e.g. John dreamed that he was rich presupposes that John was not rich. Moreover, Palmer (1976: 67) uses the word likely to refer to non-factive presupposition, as in It is likely that John came early, which presupposes that John might or might not come early.

There are forms which may be treated as the source of lexical presupposition, such as manage, stop, and start. In this type, the use of one form with its asserted meaning is conventionally interpreted with the presupposition that another (non-asserted) meaning is understood. When one says that someone managed to do something, the asserted meaning is that the person tried and succeeded in some way. But when one says that someone did not manage, the asserted meaning is that the person did not succeed. In both cases, however, there is a presupposition (non-asserted) that the person tried to do that something. So, managed is conventionally interpreted as asserting 'succeeded' and presupposing 'tried'.

In addition to the presuppositions that are associated with the use of certain words and phrases, there are also structural presuppositions. In this case, certain sentence structures have been analyzed as conventionally and regularly presupposing that part of the structure is assumed to be true (Yule, 2000: 29). One might say that speakers can use such structures to treat information as presupposed (assumed to be true) and hence to be accepted as true by the listeners. For instance, the WH forms (i.e. when, where, etc.) can be used in this type, as in When did John leave? It presupposes that John left. Acadian et al. (1997: 384) state that "the pragmatic presupposition of a sentence is the set of conditions that have to be satisfied in order for the intended speech act to be appropriate in the circumstances or to be felicitous".

The last type is called a counter-factual presupposition, in which what is presupposed is not only true, but is the opposite of what is true, or contrary to facts. For example, the sentence: If you were his friend you would have helped him presupposes that you are not his friend. A conditional structure of this sentence presupposes that the information in the if-clause is not true of the time of utterance. One can conclude that presuppositions are considered to be a matter of pragmatics not of semantics because they are not stable and having context independent aspects of meaning as it is shown in the case of defeasibility.

Pertaining to the functions of language, Roman Jakobson (1960) defined six function of language (or communicative functions), according to which an effective act of verbal communication can be described. Each of the function has associated factor. They are: the referential, the poetic, the emotive/expressive, the conative/directive, the phatic and the meta-lingual function.

The referential function corresponds to the factor of context and describes a situation, object or mental state. The poetic function focuses on "the message for its own sake" (the code itself, and how it is used) and is the operative function in poetry as well as slogans. The emotive function relates to the addresser (sender) and is best exemplified by interjections and other sound changes that do not alter the denotative meaning of an utterance but do add information

about the addresser's/speaker's internal state, e.g. "Wow, what a view!" The conative function engages the addressee/receiver directly and is best illustrated by vocatives and imperatives, e.g. "Tom! Come inside and eat!". The phatic function is language for the sake of interaction and is therefore associated with the contact/channel factor. The phatic function can be observed in greetings and casual discussions of the weather, particularly with strangers. It also provides the keys to open, maintain, verify or close the communication channel: "Hello?", "Ok", "Hummmmm", "Bye". The meta-lingual function is the use of language (what Jakobson calls "code") to discuss or describe itself.

From the description of the types of language functions based on Roman Jakobson's theory above, the researcher searched the language function of all utterances in George Orwell's Novella *Animal Farm*.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research had been conducted by using descriptive method because it described and it was suitable with the purpose of the study. According to Monsen (2008: 5) the descriptive research often illustrates a relevant but non quantified topic involving a well-focused research question. It generates narrative data that describe words instead of numbers. Its primary purpose to explore the phenomenon of interest as a prelude to the theory development. Moreover, the analysis was used in written document because the source of the data was taken from George Orwell's *Novella Animal Farm* and these data were from all of the utterances of the main and minor characters in George Orwell's *Novella Animal Farm*.

The source of the data in this research is George Orwell's *Novella Animal Farm*. and the data are taken from the utterances expressed by all character in the novella. Moreover, the data which have found in George Orwell's *Novella Animal Farm* was analyzed to classify them into types of presupposition and language function and the limited data were all main and minor character's utterances in the novella.

DISCUSSION

There were 180 utterances used as source of data in this research. The data in this movie are categorized based on the types of presupposition then, the analysed of language function is done after categorizing its type of presupposition. To analyse types of language functions of each types of presupposition, the writer analyses the language functions by using Roman Jakobson's (1960) theory.

Datum 1

Comrades," he said, "I trust that every animal here appreciates the sacrifice that Comrade Napoleon has made in taking this extra labor upon himself. Do not imagine, comrades, that leadership is a pleasure! On the contrary, it is a deep and heavy responsibility. (Chapter 5)

Context:

The utterance above happened in the animal farm where all animal gathered except Napoleon, their leader. The above utterance was said by Squealer, the spokesman of Napoleon. Squealer was a brilliant talker, and when he was arguing some difficult point he had a way of skipping from side to side and whisking his tail which was somehow very persuasive. At this moment he tries tooth and nail or as hard as he can to persuade people to accept Napoleon's idea and hegemony. From Squealer's utterance it can be presupposed that there was Napoleon and he had made the extra labour upon himself, in this case was talking about the existence and the self-sacrifice of Napoleon as a leader of the community.

Analysis:

It can be categorized from the utterance that contains two proposition p and q and it is using a symbol \gg that means 'presuppose', and then we can analyse the relationship by using this propositions.

a. I trust that every animal here appreciates the sacrifice that Comrade Napoleon has made in taking this extra labour upon himself. (= p)

b. I trust that every animal here appreciates the sacrifice that Comrade Napoleon has not made in taking this extra labour upon himself. (= Not p)

c. There was Napoleon (= q)

d. $p \gg q$, NOT $p \gg q$

It can be seen that the presupposition above is generally described as constancy under negation. It means that the presupposition of an utterance will remain constant (still true) even when that utterance is negated. The presupposition used in Squealer's utterance is existential presupposition because it conveys the existence of Napoleon.

From Squealer's utterance dealing with the Excellency of Napoleon, it can be analyzed that Napoleon is the best leader among them who had made self-sacrifice by doing extra labor upon himself. He has made self-sacrifice for the betterment of the prosperity and welfare of the community.

Based on Jakobson's theory of six language function (1960:353), this can be categorized that the function of Squealer's utterance is Referential or Representatives function. The referential function corresponds to the factor of context and describes a situation, object or mental state. The descriptive statements of the referential function can consist of both definite descriptions and deictic words. In this utterance it can be seen that cleverly Squealer persuade the citizen of animal farm to hail and glorify Napoleon by using definite descriptions and deictic words which elaborates the quality of Napoleon as the highest leader of the community. In other moment Squaler explains Napoleon as The Father of All Animals, Terror of Mankind,

Protector of the Sheep-fold, Duckling’s friend and the like. All of these “bombastic” address terms describe Napoleon.

In this research, the researcher found 180 utterances of Novella’s main character’s utterance that can be categorized to the types of presuppositions based on Yule’s theory. It was classified into existential presupposition 69 utterances (38,3%), lexical 35 utterances (19,4%), structural 53 utterances (19,4%), Factive 4 utterances (2,2%) and non-factive 19 utterance (10,6%). The occurrence of types of presupposition of all of the utterances performed into this following table.

Table 1. (the occurrences of Types of Presupposition used in George Orwell’s Novella Animal Farm’s utterances)

Types of Presupposition	Frequency	Percentage	Description
Existential	69	38,3%	triggered by definite description and possessive construction
Structural	53	29,4%	triggered by WH-question
Lexical	35	19,4%	triggered by change of state verb stop & start ; implicative predicate (the word manage); iterative (the word again)
Non-factive	19	10,6%	triggered by the verb dream & imagine
Factive	4	2,2%	triggered by factive verb/predicate aware & glad
Total	180	100%	

From the five (5) types of presupposition which used in George Orwell’s Novella Animal Farm main character’s utterances, Existential presupposition is the most dominant among all types of presupposition (69 data /38, 3%). This type shows definite noun phrase. One of the interesting findings is that the word “Comrade Napoleon” was repeated 25 times on the novella. It shows the superiority of Napoleon as the leader of the community as the result of Squealer’s propaganda in influencing other citizen of Animal Farm to give honor toward

Napoleon. Another fact of existential type are the abundant data using the phrases “our farm, our family, our land, our friends, our children” showing possessive construction.

The second finding is The structural presupposition having 53 data/ 29,4% which were triggered by WH-question like the word “what, who, where, when” which help the readers to fully understand the story of the novella. By the use of this type the reader will conventionally and regularly presupposing that part of the structure is already assumed to be true. It can be said that speakers can use such structures to treat information as presupposed (i.e. assumed to be true) and hence to be accepted as true or already known to be the case by the listener. These are the data taken from the novella:

“Now, comrades, what is the nature of this life of ours? Let us face it: our lives are miserable, laborious, and short. We are born, we are given just so much food as will keep the breath in our bodies, and those of us who are capable of it are forced to work to the last atom of our strength; and the very instant that our usefulness has come to an end we are slaughtered with hideous cruelty. No animal in England knows the meaning of happiness or leisure after he is a year old. No animal in England is free. The life of an animal is misery and slavery: that is the plain truth. (Chapter 1)

“.....And you hens, how many eggs have you laid in this last year, and how many of those eggs ever hatched into chickens? The rest have all gone to market to bring in money for Jones and his men. And you, Clover, where are those four foals you bore, who should have been the support and pleasure of your old age? Each was sold at a year old — you will never see one of them again. In return for your four confinements and all your labor in the fields, what have you ever had except your bare rations and a stall? (Chapter 1)

The third finding is the lexical presupposition having 35 data or 19.4% of the total amount of data. This type was triggered by change of state verb *stop* & *start* ; implicative predicate (the word *manage*); iterative (the word *again*). These are the data taken from the novella:

Once again this argument was unanswerable. Certainly the animals did not want Jones back; if the holding of debates on Sunday mornings was liable to bring him back, then the debates must stop. (Chapter 1)

When they had once got it by heart, the sheep developed a great liking for this maxim, and often as they lay in the field they would all start bleating “Four legs good, two legs bad! Four legs good, two legs bad!” and keep it up for hours on end, never growing tired of it. (Chapter 3)

However, these stories were never fully believed. Rumors of a wonderful farm, where the human beings had been turned out and the animals managed their own affairs, continued to circulate in vague and distorted forms, and throughout that year a wave of rebelliousness ran through the countryside (Chapter 4)

Once again the animals were conscious of a vague uneasiness. Never to have any dealings with human beings, never to engage in trade, never to make use of money — had not these been among the earliest resolutions passed at that first triumphant Meeting after Jones was expelled? All the animals remembered passing such resolutions: or at least they thought that they remembered it. (Chapter 6)

The fourth finding is the non-factive presupposition having 19 data or 10.6% from all data. It was triggered by the verb *dream* & *imagine*. These are the data taken from the novella:

“Comrades, you have heard already about the strange dream that I had last night. But I will come to the dream later. I have something else to say first. I do not think, comrades, that I shall be with you for many months longer, and before I die, I feel it my duty to pass on to you such wisdom as I have acquired. I have had a long life, I have had much time for thought as I lay alone in my stall, and I think I may say that I understand the nature of life on this earth as well as any animal now living. It is about this that I wish to speak to you. (Chapter 1)

Silent and terrified, the animals crept back into the barn. In a moment the dogs came bounding back. At first no one had been able to imagine where these creatures came from, but the problem was soon solved: they were the puppies whom Napoleon had taken away from their mothers and reared privately (chapter 5)

The last finding is factive presupposition having 4 data which is the only 2,2% from all data and it is triggered by factive verb/predicate like *aware* & *glad*. Factive is the assumption that something is true due to the presence of some verbs such as “*aware*” and “*glad*”. These are the data taken from the novella:

All that year the animals worked like slaves. But they were happy in their work; they grudged no effort or sacrifice, well aware that everything that they did was for the benefit of themselves and those of their kind who would come after them, and not for a pack of idle, thieving human beings. (Chapter 6)

The animals believed every word of it. Truth to tell, Jones and all he stood for had almost faded out of their memories. They knew that life nowadays was harsh and bare, that they were often hungry and often cold, and that they were usually working when they were not asleep. But doubtless it had been worse in the old days. They were glad to believe so. Besides, in those days they had been slaves and now they were free, and that made all the difference, as Squealer did not fail to point out. (Chapter 9)

In this research, the researcher also analyzes the language function used in George Orwell’s novella *Animal Farm* main character’s utterances. From each type of presuppositions, the researcher also analyzes which language function is mostly used in the Novella’s main character utterance.

Table 2 Graphic of Language Function used in the Novella's main character's utterances in general:

Explanation:

- First chart, Referential 57 utterances/ (47, 9%)
- Second chart, Emotive 33 utterances (27, 7%)
- Third chart, Conative 25 utterances (21, 1%)
- Fourth chart, Poetic 3 utterances (2, 5%)
- Fifth chart, Phatic 1 utterance (0, 8%)

This finding in George Orwell's novella *Animal Farm* is different from the previous studies that also analyzed about presupposition. Compared with Li (2005) from Wuhan University, studied Presupposition in Advertising Language. By qualitative analysis, Li tries to explore the functions of each type of presuppositions in advertising texts by Yule's theory. From 100 selected advertising utterances, Li found out that 85% contains presupposition and existential presupposition accounts for the largest percentage (65 %).

Meanwhile, this research found out that factive presupposition as the most type used in George Orwell's Novella *Animal Farm* utterances. Compared with Li, which is analyzed the presupposition in advertising; this research analyzed the utterances used in George Orwell's Novella *Animal Farm*. The purpose of utterances in advertising and novella should be different, because advertising used language to attract and persuade people, while in novella the utterances used as the part of conversation and emotional expression.

Wang Ying Fang (2007) also analyzed about Presupposition and its Function in advertisement based on Yule's theory. He categorized that presupposition is an adopted for language technique in advertisements. Different with Li and this research, he is emphasis his research is placed on pragmatics functions of advertising language from three angles: presupposition and advertisement, presupposition psychology and market strategies of advertisement.

Abbot (1999), in her journal's article entitled "Presupposition as Non-Assertions assumed that the assertion or presupposition distinction maps fairly directly onto the distinction between new and old information. In contrary with this research which is analyzed the presupposition used in George Orwell's novella *Animal Farm*. Among with the previous study, this research quite similar with Li's that analyze the presupposition in advertising language.

This research used descriptive method and George Yule's theory. The researcher found that existential presupposition accounts for the largest percentage (38,9%). There are 69 data of utterances of the main characters in the George Orwell's novella *Animal Farm* that can be categorized to the existential presupposition.

After classifying the types of presupposition, the writer analyzes what the information being intended in the presupposition by considering the context that influences the conversation. Therefore, the writer finds out that the context really influences the message that is delivered by the speaker. The writer can analyze the meaning of pragmatic presupposition through the context. The speakers share information and express their feeling through presupposition, it's because they need to deliver information that the speakers believe the listener already known the intended meaning.

CONCLUSION

In speaking, speaker assumes information is already known by their listener. In fact, the information isn't stated directly in speaker's utterance. To understand what the intention of speaker meaning, the listener need to make some assumptions about the speaker's utterance. Listener needs to look for word's meaning and what the speaker's mean in the same context. To avoid the misinterpretation in meaning, it will be dealt with presuppositions.

Presupposition can be defined as assumption that shared by the speaker to the listener. Presupposition can be applied in daily conversation in literary works. As the explanation above, presupposition can be applied in George Orwell's novella *Animal Farm*. The novella used five types of presuppositions. As found in Orwell's *Novella Animal Farm* mostly the utterance of the main characters contain presuppositions.

Pragmatics approach is one of the approaches that is used in conducting this analysis. Analyzing the presupposition in George Orwell's novella *Animal Farm* based on the theory of Presupposition by George Yule and the Language function by Roman Jakobson, meanwhile presupposition and language function can be analyzed not only from these theories but also from other theories. Beside that there are several objects in novella which can be analyzed by

future researcher who is interested in presupposition on this legendary classic literary work. They are politeness strategy, language style, and grammar.

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Analysis of Humor on Cartoon Comics “Be Like Bro”: Pragmatics Study

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to identify the types of violation of conversational maxims created by cartoon comic entitled “Be Like Bro” in the English version and also to describe how the humorous situation can be created from those violations. There are two findings in this research. First, those six data show that there is a violation of conversational maxims, which are the maxim of quantity, the maxim of relevance, and the maxim of manner. Those six data also show that the humorous situation is creating by incongruent meaning in the conversation and releasing the feeling.

Keywords: humor, cooperative principles, context, pragmatics

INTRODUCTION

One of the linguistic phenomena that have developed in society today is humor. Humor is a short story that tells a funny situation that can make the reader laughs because of its entertainment. According to Wijana on his book *Kartun: Studi tentang Permainan Bahasa*, humor is a form of the game which is used wordplay that can stimulate human to smile and laugh for those who see it (2003).

Nowadays, the use of humor is increasing. Many types of humor appear in the society such as comic strips, memes, humor in the movies, stand-up comedy, and another humor that can be found around us. As something that can make people laugh, humor also has a function to build a good relationship in society. There is a unique thing that can trigger the appearance of humor in a conversation that is by violating the rules of language use.

In this research, the researchers try to analyze a topic related to humor in one of the comic cartoons, *Be Like Bro* because of the development of the use and the uniqueness possessed by humor itself. The comic cartoon entitled *Be Like Bro* is already familiar, and it can be found on social media such as Facebook.

According to the background of the research, there are two problem formulations in this research. The first research question is: What are the types of violation in cooperative principle that appear in comic cartoon *Be Like Bro?* Moreover, the second is: How can the violation in cooperative principle make a humor situation in comic cartoon *Be Like Bro?* From the questions we can have two research objectives to be achieved in this research; to find out the types of violation in cooperative principle that appear in comic cartoon *Be Like Bro* and to explain how the violation in cooperative principle can make a humor situation in comic cartoon *Be Like Bro*.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Several studies have been conducted regarding the object of humor-based research. The first was carried out by Suwanto (2012) in his thesis entitled *Verbal Humor Analysis of English Language (A Case Study in the How I Met Your Mother Comedy Series)*. This thesis discusses the humor situation that occurs in that comedy series and the researcher found that there are linguistic aspects that are used to invite humor situation in this comedy. The result of this study proved that linguistic aspects such as orthographical, phonological, morphological, hyponym, antonym, euphemism, hyperbole, deixis, the connection of intra-sentential elements, the connection of intra-centric elements, and the connection between propositions are the trigger of humor situation. Also, there are several violations from the principle of cooperation, the principle of politeness, the principle of irony, and the presupposition that causes a humorous situation.

The second study was conducted by Triandana (2014) entitled *Discourse of Humor in Kill the Messenger Movie (A Case Study of Stand-Up Comedy by Christ Rock)*. This thesis aims to determine the structure of the humor in stand-up comedy, to find out the aspect of pragmatics that creates humor, to find out language aspects and the function of the humor in stand-up comedy. As a result, there are various structures, and patterns such as one-liners, questions and answers, simple structures, and complex structures are used in this movie. There are also some linguistic aspects such as morphology, syntax, semantics, deixis, and language style that can be factors to create humor situation in the film. In the end, the researcher also finds that solidarity, power, and psychology are the functions that can be found in humor in that movie.

According to the explanation from the researches above, this research has a different research object compared with both of the researches. The object of the research taken by Suwanto (2012) is comic strips, and Triandana (2014) took the film as his research object while this research uses the comic cartoon as the object. Furthermore, this research also develops the problem formulations related to the violation of cooperative principle and how those violations.

PRAGMATIC THEORY

Pragmatic is a branch of linguistics that focuses on the meaning of the speech. Levinson (1983:21) defined pragmatics as the study of the relationship between language and its context as a basis to understand the speech which is delivered. Another definition of pragmatics is also stated by Yule (1996:3-4) which states that pragmatics examines the relation between linguistic forms and the user of the linguistic forms.

According to Yule (1996), there are four areas in the pragmatic study. First, pragmatics is the study of the meaning behind the speaker's words. It means that pragmatics try to analyze what is meant by the speaker behind the words expressed. Second, pragmatics is the study of meaning in a context. It proves that pragmatics can examine how speakers organize their words according to the context and the situation when they speak. Third, pragmatics examines that sometimes speech is not directly expressed by the speaker. The last, pragmatics explains how things can be expressed based on the closeness between the speaker and the listener.

In conclusion from the explanation above, it can be said that pragmatics is the study of the meaning of a speech. By using pragmatic approach, people can learn about the meaning of speech, the assumption that arises from the speech, and the action shown by them when there is a conversation between the speaker and the listener.

Context

Context is an essential element in the pragmatic study. A researcher must pay attention to the context in a conversation in doing practical research. According to Cutting (2002), there are three types of contexts in the pragmatic study: (1) Situational Context, this context is related to the time and place where the conversation is taking place, (2) Background Knowledge Context, this context is related to the existing cultural background and also related to individual relations in a conversation, (3) Co-textual Context, related to the content contained in a text.

Conversational Implicature

Conversational Implicature mainly refers to the collaboration carried out by the speaker and the listener in conducting a conversation. According to Yule (1996: 35), it means that in a conventional implicature, sometimes specific intentions are not discussed but are in a conversation. An example of a conventional impression can be seen through the following example:

Mars: Did you do the homework?

Venus: I was sick last night.

Based on the brief example above, Mars hopes that Venus answers the question related to the questions he asked. However, the question is not answered with yes, I did the homework or no, I did not do the homework, but the answers *I was sick last night*. The sentence *I was sick last night* shows that Venus is not doing her homework because he was sick. Therefore, in a conversation, it is expected that the listener can understand the meaning implied in a conversation.

The Cooperative Principle

According to Grice (in Wijana, 2003), four maxims must be obeyed by the participant in the speech act in a conversation. The maxim consists of the maxim of quantity, the maxim of quality, the maxim of relevance, and the maxim of manner.

Maxim of Quantity

Based on the maxim of quantity, each conversation should contribute as much as possible or as much as the other person needs. Examples of maxim quantity are as follows:

Anthony: George, did you buy the apple juice?

George: Yes, I bought the apple juice.

According to the conversation above, George is very cooperative in responding to the questions from Anthony. What became George adequately answered a question from Anthony.

Maxim of Quality

Maxim of quality requires the participants to tell the truth. According to Yule (1996), this type demands not to say what you believe to be false and do not say that for which you lack adequate evidence.

Teacher: Why did you finish your homework last night?

Frans: I needed to take a rest because I was sick last night.

Based on the conversation, the teacher hopes to find out the reason why Frans did not finish his homework last night. During the conversation, Frans answered honestly that he had not finished his homework because he was sick. If Frans answered the question from the teacher honestly, it means he is not lying and does not violate the maxim of quality.

Maxim of Relevance

Maxim of relevance requires each participant to make a contribution that is relevant to the issue of the conversation (Wijana, 2003: 58).

Mother: Ani, there is a telephone.

Ani: I am in the restroom, ma'am.

If it is observed, the conversation implies that at that time Ani could not answer the telephone directly. Indirectly Ani asked for help so that his mother received the call. According to this example, it can be seen that the maxim of relevance does not only arise from its spoken meaning but also can arise by the implications of the speech.

Maxim of Manner

Maxim of manner requires that each participant in the conversation should speak directly, not blurred, not excessive, and expected to be coherent (Wijana, 2003).

Alex: John, I like your jacket. Where did you buy it?

John: Thank you. I bought it at Implora Distro next to our campus.

According to the conversation above, John has provided complete information by what was asked by Alex. John mentioned the name of the distribution where he bought a jacket, even the location of the distro. Therefore, what John said is following the maxim of manner.

Violation of Cooperative Principle

According to Wijana (2003), there are four types of violation of cooperative principle in pragmatic studies: (1) Violation in the maxim of quantity occurs when the participant does not provide as much information or as much as needed by the other person. (2) The violation in the maxim of quality occurs when the participants do not say the truth. (3) The violation in the maxim of relevance occurs when the participant does not make relevant contributions in a conversation. (4) The violation in the maxim of manner occurs when the participant speaks in an unclear, too excessive and not coherent.

Theory of Humor

Ross in his book *Language of Humor* (1998) defined the word humor as something that makes people laugh or smile. Humour usually occurs because of violations made by the participants. The definition of humor by Ross is also reinforced by a statement of humor by Attardo (1994): "Many linguists have taken humor as a category which converses any events or objects that elucidate laughter, amuses, or feels to be funny."

According to Attardo (1994: 47), the situation of humor can be formed because of the violation of the cooperative principle between participants in the conversation. There are several classifications of humor theory according to Attardo (1994):

Incongruity Theory

This humor occurs because of irregularities or the difference between what is expected and what happens later. Based on this theory, the situation of humor can be created because of an understanding of the various kinds of meanings implied by a word, the existence of an ambiguity, and the existence of irregularities in a conversation.

Hostility Theory

This humor occurs when one of the speech act participants feels the 'victory' suddenly because the participant of the speech act feels more potent than the other speech act participants.

Release Theory

This theory sees humor as something that can trigger one's tension and energy as an effect of the pressure on the situation around or on the mind. Through humor, people who feel depressed tend to laugh as hard as they can to reduce their feelings of distress.

METHODOLOGY

This research is a qualitative descriptive study in which *Be Like Bro* cartoon comic data is taken from a Facebook account. Four hundred twenty-seven photo chronologies are related to the problem of humor, but the researchers only limit the dialogue that occurs between two figures named Bro and Bro that were uploaded during 2017. The researchers applies pragmatic theory, context, and conversational implicature, to see the situation of real comedy. Then the theory of cooperative principle and the theory of violation in cooperative principle are used to see the deviation of the cooperative principle as what happened in the *Be Like Bro* funny cartoon as well as the answer to the first problem statement. Furthermore, the theory of humor will be used by researchers to answer the second problem formulation related to how the violation of cooperative principle can create a humour situation in the comic cartoon.

DISCUSSION

1. Violation of Cooperative Principle

Data 1

The comic cartoon was uploaded on April 7, 2017. The situation in the dialogue for this comic cartoon occurred when Bro 1 met Bro 2. The topic of the conversation between the two was related to information that Bro 1 would marry his girlfriend. If there is good cooperation in the conversation, then when Bro 2 asks 'when will you get married,' Bro 1 should answer explicitly according to the date on which they will marry so that the answer from Bro 1 is the answer expected by Bro 2. However, the reality is when Bro 2 asks "Wow. When?" Bro 1 replied with "Me on March 15 and my girlfriend on August 27". Based on this, it can be seen that Bro 1 violates the maxim of relevance because Bro 1 does not build the same context as the context built by Bro 2. The context understood by Bro 2 is the date on which both (Bro 1 and his girlfriend) will marry, while the answer from Bro 1 is the date on which both will get married, but on different dates. That means in reality, both of them have separated, and both will be married to their respective partners.

Data 2

The comic cartoon was uploaded on February 13, 2017. The situation in the *Be Like Bro* comic cartoon happened when Bro 1 met Bro 2. Through the short conversation above, Bro 1 asked Bro 2 what kind of Apple brand gadgets Bro 2 could buy, according to the amount of money in Bro 2's account. If the conversation is built by the principle of the maxim, then the answer that should be raised by Bro 2 is an iPhone, iPad, or mac book. However, in reality, Bro 2 answers "Apple juice" where the answer from Bro 2 is not by the expectations of questions from Bro 1. It shows that the answer from Bro 2 violates the maxim of relevance because the answer does not reflect the answer desired by the questioner.

Also, we can also see that there are other meanings implied by the answers that Bro 2 said. When Bro 1 asks "With your current account balance, which Apple product can you buy?" Then Bro 2 answers "Apple juice." This also confirms that basically the amount of money on Bro 2's account is not much, the money can only be used to buy apple juice which is the cost is under Rp 10,000, -

Data 3

The comic cartoon was uploaded on January 21, 2017. The situation that occurred in the dialogue was when Bro 1 met Bro 2. Bro 1 was curious about what Bro 2 was doing, so he asked: "Hey bro, what's up?" Also, Bro 2 said "Nothing much. They were converting oxygen into carbon dioxide". Because Bro 1 still did not understand Bro 2's answer, he asked again about the purpose of things being done by Bro 2, and Bro 2 answers "Breathing ... Dude". Based on the short conversation above, there is a violation of the maxim of quantity, because the sentence from Bro 2 "Nothing much. Converting oxygen into carbon dioxide" is too much, making Bro 1 unable to capture the intended answer. If Bro 2 responded directly to the word "Breathing ... dude", then there will be no violation on the maxim of quantity.

Data 4

The comic cartoon was uploaded on January 15, 2017. The situation occurred when Bro 1 met Bro 2, and they had a short conversation. Through this brief conversation, Bro 1 asked Bro 2 about what shampoo, soap, and brand lotions used by Bro 2 in his daily life. To create cooperation in a conversation, when Bro 1 ask "Which shampoo do you use?" (And so on), Bro 2 should answer explicitly the name of shampoo, soap, and lotion that he uses in his daily life. However, there is a violation of the maxim of a manner in the dialogue. After several times Bro 2 answered the question, it turned out that what Bro 2 meant was not the name of shampoo, soap, and lotion used. Bro 2 only answers "No! Mark is my roommate! " at the end of the conversation. It proves that Bro 2 has vague, unclear, and not directly to the point of answering the question. Besides, the last answer from Bro 2 also has no line with the expectations of the Bro 1 because, in the conversation, both of them have different concepts.

Data 5

The comic cartoon was uploaded on January 16, 2017. It told about Bro 1 and Bro 2 who talked about the date and year of Bro 1's birthday. If there was good cooperation in the conversation, then when Bro 1 asked "Which year?", Bro 2 should answer with the year of his birthday. In reality, Bro 2 replied with "Every year, bro." This shows that in the conversation, there is a violation on the maxim of relevance because the answer from Bro 2 deviated from the context proposed by Bro 1, even though Bro 2's answer is correct because we celebrate birthdays every year.

Data 6

The comic cartoon was uploaded on April 5, 2017. The situation in the conversation occurred when Bro 1 met Bro 2. Both of them had a dialogue about what gift Bro 1 should give to his girlfriend. However, the answer made by Bro 2 was not in line with the expectation of Bro 1. Instead, Bro 2 offers Bro 1 to give his telephone number to the boyfriend Bro 1. This of course violates the maxim of manner, because Bro 2 should be able to give clear answer for what Bro 1 asked.

The Violation of the Cooperative Principle Can Create Humor Situation

The mismatch between what is expected by someone and what happens in the conversation.

Based on the humor theory that has been described, the violation of cooperative principle can create a humorous situation because of an odd idea or perception between what is expected by someone and the reality that occurs in the conversation. This can be seen in data numbers 1, 2, 4, 5, and 6. The conversations in comic cartoons occur because of the difference between what answers are expected and the reality of the answers in the conversation.

For example data number 1. Bro 2 asks about the date of the wedding to be held by Bro 1 and his girlfriend. Logically, the answer given by Bro 1 refers to a date on which they will be officially married. However, in reality, the answers given are not in line with the expectations asked by Bro 2. The incompatibility of what is expected also occurs in comic cartoons number 2, 4, 5 and 6.

Feeling release to express something in excess.

Based on the humor theory that has been described, it is found a comic cartoon where the humor situation is created from excessive feelings towards something. It can be seen in data 3, where Bro 2 answers Bro 1's question excessively "Nothing much — converting oxygen into carbon dioxide". The answer from Bro 2 shows how he is very expressive in explaining something, even though Bro 2 actually can explain Bro 2 through a simpler word, which is 'breathing'.

CONCLUSION

The results of the current analysis reveal that the violation of the cooperative principle can create a humorous situation. From total six data used in this research, the data number 1,2,4,5, and 6 lead to the mismatch between what is expected by someone and what actually happens in the conversation and it creates humorous situation. It is in accordance with Attardo (1994) statement that the humor situation can be create because of the violation of the cooperative principle between participants in the conversation. This research only covers a certain amount of time which was during 2017 and is only limited by conversation conducted by characters Bro and Bro. Further research can be carried out broadly, for example with comic cartoon humor involving more than two participants and in a longer period of time. In addition, this research can also be analysed deeply by examining the function of humor presented in a comic cartoon.

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Analysis on Politeness Principle in Kung Fu Panda 1

The movie

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ABSTRACT

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This article aims to identify the types of violation of conversational maxims created by cartoon comic entitled “Be Like Bro” in the English version and also to describe how the humorous situation can be created from those violations. There are two findings in this research. First, those six data show that there is a violation of conversational maxims, which are the maxim of quantity, the maxim of relevance, and the maxim of manner. Those six data also show that the humorous situation is creating by incongruent meaning in the conversation and releasing the feeling.

Keywords: Pragmatics, Politeness principle, Movie.

INTRODUCTION

Language is a tool which used to communicate and to deliver our ideas. According to Raymond Williams (1977: 21), language is a definition of human being in the world which always explains something implicitly or explicitly. It is because language is involved in every aspect of human experience, and creates as well as reflect image of that experience. Therefore, it is impossible to imagine human being without language.

The specific study which studied about language called Linguistics. There are many types of Linguistics. Those are Micro Linguistics and Macro Linguistics. In Micro Linguistics, it consists of Phonetics and Phonology, Morphology, Syntax, Pragmatics, and Semantics. In Macro Linguistics, it consists of Psycholinguistic, Sociolinguistics and Anthro-linguistics. All of those branches have specific field to be studied. The branches which studied about speaker’s meaning called Pragmatics.

According to Yule (1996), Pragmatics is the study which concerned with the meaning as communicated by a speaker (or writer) and interpreted by a listener (or reader). In addition, Pragmatics studies about the language and its context in a community of speech. Furthermore, we have to be polite using the language to communicate in a community. The part of pragmatics which focuses on studying about politeness called Politeness Principle. Leech defines politeness as forms of behavior that establish and maintain comity. Politeness principle usually used in a school life between teacher and students, between parents and children, between the older and the younger and so on.

Indeed, after watching the movie Kung Fu Panda 1, the writers found phenomena about the use of politeness principle in Kung Fu’s circumstance. It makes the writers are interested in knowing more about politeness principle used in the movie Kung Fu Panda 1 and knowing more about the applying of each politeness principle in conversations. Therefore, the writers conduct some research questions as follows:

1. What is the type politeness principle used in the movie Kung Fu Panda 1?
2. What is the most and the least maxim usually used in the movie Kung Fu Panda 1?

3. How do the figures in the movie Kung Fu Panda 1 use politeness principle in the communication?

LITERATURE REVIEW

There are some definitions about pragmatics that can help us to understand it deeply. Grundy (2000, p.3) states: "Pragmatics is about explaining how we produce and understand such every day, but apparently rather peculiar uses of language." It means that pragmatics, the study explains us how to produce utterances and comprehend what people say in daily conversation although maybe they use unfamiliar language.

Levinson (1983, p.9) gives a definition that pragmatics is the study of those relations between language and context that are grammaticalized, or encoded in the structure of a language. This means pragmatics has relation with grammar because what we will say must grammatically correct. Thus, this study cause us learn how to make utterances that are right in grammar and the hearer can interpret the meaning. Besides, pragmatics is a systematic way of explaining the language use in context. It seeks to explain aspects of meaning which cannot be found in the plain sense of words or structures, as explained by semantics.(Moore, 2003).

Leech (1983, p.11) explains that general pragmatics is abstraction between the study of language in total abstraction from the situation, and the study of more socially specialized uses of language. Hence, it is clear that pragmatics is the study about the relation between language and context that are used in the community.

From the definitions above, it can be concluded that pragmatics is a field linguistics study which does not only explain about language but also explain how to produce and understand the language use in our real life following the factors that influence the language choice. It teaches us how to apply it in our daily life.

Politeness Principle

The politeness principle is a series of maxims, which Geoff Leech has proposed as a way of explaining how politeness operates in conversational exchanges. Leech defines politeness as forms of behaviour that establish and maintain comity. That is the ability of participants in a social interaction to engage in interaction in an atmosphere of relative harmony. In stating his maxims Leech uses his own terms for two kinds of illocutionary acts. He calls *representatives* "assertives", and calls *directives* "impositives".

- Each maxim is accompanied by a sub-maxim (between square brackets), which is of less importance. These support the idea that negative politeness (avoidance of discord) is more important than positive politeness (seeking concord)
- Not all of the maxims are equally important. For instance, *tact* influences what we say more powerfully than does *generosity*, while *approbation* is more important than *modesty*.
- Note also that speakers may adhere to more than one maxim of politeness at the same time. Often one maxim is on the forefront of the utterance, with a second maxim being invoked by implication.
- If politeness is not communicated, we can assume that the politeness attitude is absent.

Leech proposed six types of Politeness Principle, such as tact maxim, generosity maxim, approbation maxim, modesty maxim, agreement maxim and sympathy maxim, which as follows:

1. Tact Maxim (A1)
 - Minimize cost to other.
 - Maximize benefit to other.
2. Generosity Maxim (A2)
 - Minimize benefit to self.
 - Maximize cost to self.
3. Approbation Maxim (A3)
 - Minimize dispraise.
 - Maximize praise of other.

4. Modesty Maxim (A4)
 - Minimize praise of self.
 - Maximize dispraise of self.
5. Agreement Maxim (A5)
 - Minimize disagreement between self and other.
 - Maximize agreement between self and other.
6. Sympathy Maxim (A6)
 - Minimize antipathy between self and other.
 - Maximize sympathy between self and other.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The approach for studying Kung Fu Panda 1 is a descriptive qualitative method. It's because a qualitative approach is a research procedure that produces the descriptive data in the form of written words. The data sources in this study are the utterances in video movie of Kung Fu Panda 1 which is downloaded from YouTube. Furthermore, the writers make a field note so that it could be easier to analyze the Politeness Principle found in the movie. In this case, the researcher conducted observation and transcript analysis. Furthermore, to know the frequency of the most and the least politeness principle used in the movie, the writers used quantitative analysis.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

The data were the scripts of Kung Fu Panda 1 below which analyzed by Politeness Principle in detail. This research discovered that all types of maxims were violated and they were shown in percentage in the following table.

The percentage overview of Politeness Principle found in Kung Fu Panda 1 as follows:

No	Kind of maxim	Symbol	Frequency	$X = \frac{F}{N} \times 100\%$
1	Tact maxim	A1	10	9,8 %
2	Generosity maxim	A2	5	4,9 %
3	Approbation maxim	A3	24	23,5 %
4	Modesty maxim	A4	11	10,8 %
5	Agreement maxim	A5	45	44,1 %
6	Sympathy maxim	A6	7	6,9 %
Total			102	100 %

Table above shows that there are 102 utterances of Politeness Principle in Kung Fu Panda 1 Movie. First, there are 10 utterances (9,8%) of tact maxim. Second, there are 5 utterances (4,9%) of generosity maxim. Third, there are 24 utterances (23,5%) of approbation maxim. Fourth, there are 11 utterances (10,8%) of modesty maxim. Fifth, there are 45 utterances (44,1%) of agreement maxim. Sixth, there are 7 utterances (6,9%) of sympathy maxim.

The most or the first maxim which is usually used in Kung Fu Panda 1 is agreement maxim which is up to 45 utterances (44,1 %). Here, it showed that the figures in the movie maximize agreement between self and other. Besides, the figures also minimize disagreement between self and other. It also shows that in a culture of Kung Fu, the agreement between Master and students is high although the students in the fact disagree with the Master. However, because the culture emphasizes the politeness between Master and the students therefore the students mostly agree with what the Master said to them.

The least maxim which is rarely used in Kung Fu Panda 1 is generosity maxim. There are 5 utterances (4,9%) used in the movie of Kung Fu Panda 1. Generosity maxim used to minimize benefits to self and maximize cost to self.

After discussing about the frequency of the most and the least maxim used in Kung Fu Panda 1, here are some of the finding's example of politeness maxim found in the movie Kung Fu Panda 1.

1. Tact Maxim

Example 1:

00:03:54 – 00:03:56 PO:*[to customer]* Oh, careful, that soup is... sharp! (A1)

Analysis:

In that utterance, Po was serving his customer who bought a bowl of soup noodle. Because Po gave attention to his customer satisfying, Po warned his customer that the bowl of soup noodle was sharp. In that utterance, the word 'sharp' meant 'hot'. Thus, in that utterance, Po maximized the benefit of his customer in order to increase the satisfying of his customer. Therefore, it included in Tact Maxim.

Example 2:

00:16:27 – 00:16:29 TIGRESS: Forgive us, Master. *[She kneels forward and bows. The others follow suit.]* We have failed you. (A4)

00:16:30 – 00:16:35 SHIFU: No. If the panda has not quit by morning, then *I* will have failed you. (A1)

Analysis:

The second part of the utterances included into Tact Maxim. It was because in that case Master Shifu maximized the benefit for his students. He chose to take the responsibility of the mistake in choosing Po as the Dragon Warrior to himself rather than to his students. He minimized the cost in taking the responsibility to his students so that later on they did not blame themselves. Furthermore, Master Shifu did not want his students to think that they were failed to become a warrior.

2. Generosity Maxim

Example 1:

00:03:39 – 00:03:40 MR. PING: What were you dreaming about? *[He puts down the basket and begins chopping vegetables next to Po as he listens.]*

00:03:41 – 00:03:47 PO: What was I... uh... I was dreaming about... *[He sees Mr. Ping listening expectantly, and can't bring himself to say the truth. He glances down at the bowl he's holding.]* Uh... noodles. (A2)

Analysis:

The utterance above inclined to be Generosity Maxim. It was because in that part Po chose to maximize the happiness for his father by saying that he dreamed about noodle although the fact was he dreamed about Kung Fu. He did not want to see his father's sadness if he said the truth. He minimized the happiness for his self because he knew that his father happiness was more important than telling him about the truth dream.

Example 2:

00:47:58-00:48:01 SHIFU: Our only hope... is the Dragon Warrior.

00:48:02-00:48:02 TIGRESS: The *panda*?

00:48:03-00:48:03 SHIFU: Yes, the *panda*! (A5)

00:48:04-00:48:06 TIGRESS: Master, *please*! Let us stop Tai Lung, this is what you've trained us for! (A2)

Analysis:

In those utterances, they talked about Tai Lung who escaped from the jail and wanted to revenge to the Valley. The destiny to stop Tai Lung belonged to Po. However, Tigress asked to Shifu that she want to stop Tai Lung. She and the Furious Five sacrifice their selves to face Tai Lung because Po did not master the Kung Fu yet. This utterance belongs to Generosity Maxim because Tigress minimized benefit to self and she maximized the cost to self.

3. Approbation Maxim

Example 1:

00:37:00 - 00:37:01 VIPER: Are you ready?

00:37:01 - 00:37:02 PO: I was born ready--

00:37:02 - 00:37:03 PO: OW! Oh...

00:37:04 - 00:37:06 VIPER: I'm sorry, brother! I thought you said you were ready!

00:37:07 - 00:37:09 PO: That was *awesome!* Let's go again. [*salutes*](A3)

Analysis:

In those utterances, Po talked to Viper when they were doing exercise. While doing an exercise, Po has to fight with Viper who was strong. Po could not equalize Viper's power and he hit by viper. Although Po feel the pain because of viper's attack, he praise the power of Viper. Because here Po maximize praise to another, it include in Approbation Maxim.

Example 2:

00:45:09-00:45:10 PO: Hope you like it.

00:45:12-00:45:14 MANTIS: [*Takes a sip.*] This is really *good!* (A3)

00:45:15-00:45:19 PO: [*Bashful*] No, c'mon. You should try my dad's secret ingredient soup. He actually... *knows* the secret ingredient.

00:45:20-00:45:22 VIPER: What are you talking about? This is amazing. (A3)

Analysis:

In those utterances, Mantis and Viper talked to Po and told him that the soup that was made by Po was delicious. Po replied that his noodle was not delicious as what his father made because his father had a secret ingredient. But, Viper praised that Po's noodle was delicious without the secret ingredient. Therefore, it include in Approbation Maxim because Mantis and Viper minimize dispraise to another nad maximize praise to another.

4. Modesty Maxim

Example 1:

00:15:58 – 00:16:08 SHIFU: Master, Master wait! That flabby panda can't possibly be the answer to... our problem! You were about to point at Tigress and that *thing* fell in front of her! That was just an accident!

00:16:09 – 00:16:11 OOGWAY: There are no accidents.

00:16:27 – 00:16:29 TIGRESS: Forgive us, Master. [*She kneels forward and bows. The others follow suit.*] We have failed you. (A4)

Analysis:

In those utterances, Tigress talks to Master Shifu that she had failed him. Therefore, one of the Furious Five was not chosen as the Dragon Warrior. Tigress minimized praise of her self by apologizing to Master Shifu. She maximize dispraise of herself by telling that she and the Furious Five has failed Master Shifu who had trained them well to be the Dragon Warrior but no one was chosen as the Dragon Warrior. Indeed, it included in Modesty Maxim.

Example 2:

00:30:21 - 00:30:39 PO: How's Shifu ever going to turn me into the Dragon Warrior? [*He lifts his belly and drops it, causing it to bounce until he stops with his his paw. He sighs.*] I mean, I'm not like the Five. I've got no claws, no wings, no venom. Even Mantis has those... [*imitating a mantis's front legs*] ...*thingies*. Maybe I should just quit and go back to making noodles. (A4)

Analysis:

In that utterance, Po talked to Master Oogway that he did not have any special thing to be a warrior, moreover to be the Dragon Warrior. Here, Po maximized dispraise of his self by saying that the only thing he had just flabby belly. Furthermore, he minimized praised to his self by saying that he should quit and go back to make noodle because he was not the Dragon Warrior and his place is not in Jade Palace. Therefore, that utterance included in Modesty Maxim.

5. Agreement Maxim

Example 1:

00:07:06 – 00:07:14 SHIFU: Fly to Chorh-Gom Prison and tell them to double the guards, double their weapons. Double everything! Tai Lung does not leave that prison!

00:07:14 – 00:07:15 ZENG: Yes, Master Shifu! (A5)

Analysis:

In that utterance, Zeng talked to his master, Shifu that he agreed with his master statement to fly to Chorh-Gom Prison and tell them to make double the guards, double their weapons and double everything so that Tai Lung does not leave that prison. Zeng minimized disagreement between his self and master Shifu by saying and maximized agreement between his self and Master Shifu by saying agree to do what Master Shifu instructed to him. Therefore, it include in Agreement Maxim.

Example 2:

00:02:10 – 00:02:10 MONKEY: We should hang out.

00:02:12 – 00:02:12 LEGENDARY WARRIOR: Agreed. (A5)

Analysis:

In that conversation, it showed that Monkey asked legendary warriors to hang out after they defeated the enemies. Because all of them were tired after a war, they agreed to Monkey's suggestion to hang out. Here, legendary warriors minimized disagreement themselves to another and maximize agreement between themselves and another. Therefore, it included in Agreement Maxim.

6. Sympathy Maxim

Example 1:

00:07:23 – 00:07:28 SHIFU: [*He rushes back to Oogway.*] W-we have to do something. We can't just let him march on the Valley and take his revenge! He'll, he'll--

00:07:28 – 00:07:40 OOGWAY: [*He looks into the water of the Moon Pool.*] Your mind is like this water, my friend. When it is agitated, it becomes difficult to see. But if you allow it to settle, the answer becomes clear. (A6)

Analysis:

In that utterance, Ooway saw Shifu's anxiety because Tai Lung was escaped from prison. Then, Oogway stated advice to make Shifu felt better. Thus, in that utterance, Ooway trying to settle down Shifu's anxiety in order to make shifu feels better. Therefore it included Sympathy Maxim.

Example 2:

00:13:41 – 00:13:43 MR. PING: Po!? [*He appears at the top of the stairs, holding Po's apron. He sees Po sitting on the fireworks chair.*] What are you doing?! [*He rushes forward and attempts to blow out the fuse.*]

00:13:44 – 00:13:48 PO: What does it look like I'm doing?! No, stop, stop! I'm going to see the Dragon Warrior!

00:13:53 – 00:13:56 MR. PING: But I don't understand. You finally had the noodle dream!

00:13:57 – 00:14:00 PO: I lied. I don't dream about noodles, Dad!

00:14:03 – 00:14:11 PO: I LOVE KUNG FUUUUUUUUUUUUUUUUUUUUU!!...

00:14:19 – 00:14:23 MR. PING: Oh, come on, son. Let's get back to work. (A6)

Analysis:

In that conversation, Mr. Ping saw Po with feeling compassionate because Po's dream about Kung Fu. Then, Mr. Ping invited Po to continue the work and no more daydream. In that utterance showed about Mr. Ping feeling sadness because he cannot do anything to make Po's dream coming true. He showed his sympathy to his beloved son by asking him to go back to work and continued to live the real world. Therefore it included Sympathy Maxim.

CONCLUSION

Pragmatics is the study of the speaker's meaning. It deals with producing and understanding the language usage in our real life. A specific study in pragmatics, which discusses about forms of politeness of behavior, called Politeness Principle. There are six types of politeness maxim proposed by Leech, such as tact maxim, generosity maxim, approbation maxim, modesty maxim, agreement maxim, and sympathy maxim. The result of the study shows that all politeness maxim is used in the movie with the frequency tact maxim 10 utterances (9,8%), generosity maxim 5 utterances (4,9%), approbation maxim 24 utterances (23,5%), modesty maxim 11 utterances (10,8%), agreement maxim 45 utterances (44,1%), and sympathy maxim 7 utterances (6,9%).

According to the data, the frequency of the most used maxim in the movie is agreement maxim which is up to 45 utterances (44,1%). It's because in a culture of Kung Fu, students mostly agree with what the Master said. They rarely disagree with their Master because disagreement shows indiscipline and it is fatal in a relationship between students and the Master. Agreement maxim used to minimize disagreement between self and maximize agreement between self and other.

The frequency of the least maxim used in the movie is generosity maxim in 5 utterances (4,9%). Generosity maxim rarely used to minimize benefit to self and maximize cost to self. Here, generosity maxim used in order to maximize the happiness of Po's father and done by Po himself. Generosity rarely used here because the most standing out point in a Kung Fu circumstance is the obedience between Master and students which is showed in the agreement between Master and students.

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The Analysis of Declaration of Illocutionary Acts of the Korean-English Drama “I Hear Your Voice”

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ABSTRACT

This study deals with the types of declaration of illocutionary acts in the Korean-English Drama “I Hear Your Voice”. The objectives of this study are (1) to find and classify the utterances in the English subtitle of the Korean drama entitled “I Hear Your Voice” that belongs to declaration of illocutionary acts, (2) to analyze the implication of the declaration of illocutionary act found in the Korean English drama “I Hear Your Voice”. This research applies descriptive qualitative method. The objects of this study are English Subtitles of the drama in episode 8 to 13 which is containing the utterances of Declaration of Illocutionary Acts. The researcher found 40 declaration of illocutionary act utterance which is divided into five types of Declaration of Illocutionary acts and the dominant types was Sentencing. For specific result, the researcher provided the percentage in detail; Resigning (5%) in 2 data, Demising (12,5%) in 5 data, Naming (17,5%) in 7 data, Appointing (20%) in 8 data, and Sentencing (45%) in 12 data. The implication of the result of this research toward English Language Teaching is that this research could be authentic material by teachers or lecturers to teach Pragmatic especially about Speech Acts.

Key words: Declaration, Illocutionary acts, Speech acts.

INTRODUCTION

Language is the most important thing in the society. Language enables people to communicate, cooperate and get along each other. Language is a system used by the people to gain information. Through the language, the humans are able to communicate properly. The language makes the interaction happened. However, common people make interaction and communication unstructured, but still the most important is that their speech can be understood and accepted by others. George Yule (1996:47) also said that in the effort to express and asserting himself, people are not only produce grammatical structure sentences, but they also produce or show actions in

that language. Therefore, there is always a meaning behind the speech utter by people. It is called speech act.

Speech act is an action which is used to make such as; requesting, informing, commanding and questioning (Cahyono, 1994:224). According to Austin, the sentences are not only utilized to utter something, to give direction to other, but also are utilized to do something actively (Cahyono, 1995:223). The sentences cannot be used to respond true or false statement. Sentence and utterance stated by Austin are called performatives.

Moreover, Austin in Levinson (1983:236) cited by Cahyono (1995:224) classified speech act to be three parts and the parts are implemented at the same time. First, locutionary act is a locution a word or sentence based on meaning and the reference, sometimes is called speaker's utterance. Second, illocutionary act is a statement, offering, promise, and other utterance or performative expression directly, sometimes is called speaker's intention. On the basis Searle's categories of illocution act, Searle defined to some parts. Third, perlocutionary act is an affect that is produces by hearer because utterance sentence and reaction from that, or sometimes is called hearer's reaction. The effect such as; persuade, deceive encourage, irritate, frighten, amuse, inspire, impress, distract, relieve tension, embarrass, attract attention and bore.

Based on Searle there are five categories of illocutionary act they are; representative, directive, commissive, expressive, and declaration. Declarative is a speech act that changes the reality in accord with the proposition of the declaration. Representatives are the types of speech acts that commit the speaker in believing something to be truth. Directives are the expressions in order to direct the hearer to do something such as; suggesting, commanding, or order something. Commissives are the expressions used by the speakers to commit themselves to do some future actions such as; promising, threatening, refusing, and pledging. And the last is declarative which is speech act used to announce something clearly and have direct change to the world through certain utterances (Yule, 1996:53-54).

According to Leech (1983: 105), declarations are illocutionary whose successful performances bring about the correspondence between the propositional content and reality e.g.

resigning, demising, christening, naming, excommunicating, appointing, sentencing, etc. Yule (1996:53) inserted that this kind of speech acts can change the world via utterance.

Example: *Priest: I pronounce you husband and wife*

Referee: you're out!

Jury foreman: we find the defendant guilty

In using a declaration the speaker changes the world via word. This kind of speech act is very special and used in very special circumstances which the expression used to change the world via utterances. This kind of speech acts are really rarely to be used, because only by a certain institutional role and in a specific context. The table below gives a brief understanding about the relationship between speech act types and language functions, which was following Searle's though (Yule 1996:53-55)

Table 1 The General Function of Speech Act According to Searle

Speech act type	Direction of fit	S= speaker X= situation
Representative	Make words fit the world	S believe x
Directive	Make the world fit the world	S wants x
Commissive	Make the world fit the words	S intend x
Cxpressive	Make the words fit the world	S feels x
Declaration	World change the world	S cause x

George Yule. 1996. Pragmatics. P 54-55

Based on the above explanation, the researcher interested to find and analyze the declaration illocutionary acts on fiction literature to give more understanding about illocutionary act. The researcher chooses the Korean-English drama entitled "I Hear Your Voice" to analyze the declaration of illocutionary acts found on the conversation in this drama. The researcher chooses the English subtitle of Korean drama "I Hear Your Voice", because the themes in this drama are about crime, judges, and law. There are many utterances including the declaration of illocutionary acts. The researcher would like to present the reason chooses this drama as the object of the study. According to Searle cited by Leech (1991:105-106), stated that declaration illocutionary act is

"A very special category of speech acts; they are performed, normally speaking, by someone who is especially authorized to do so within some institutional framework (classical examples are judges sentencing offenders, ministers of religion christening

babies, dignitaries naming ships, etc). The person who makes a declaration uses language as an outward sign that some institution (social, religious, legal, etc) action is performed”.

Considering, Searle’s statement above, the researcher interesting in conducting this research which focuses on a very special category of speech act, which is only can be performed by a special person in a special circumstances. *I Hear Your Voice* is a Korean drama which is told about the crimes, judgments, and court. The actors in this drama also act as lawyers, prosecutors, judges and police which people who have special authorized to do so within some institutional frameworks and make a declaration uses language as an outward sign that some institution actions were performed. Therefore the researcher interested in conducting analysis in the research entitled “*THE ANALYSIS OF DECLARATION OF ILLOCUTIONARY ACTS IN THE KOREAN-ENGLISH DRAMA “I HEAR YOUR VOICE”*”.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this research, the researcher used descriptive qualitative research method. Qualitative research method is defined as a research procedure which produces descriptive data in the form of words written or spoken of the person (Bogdan and Taylor 1975:5 in Moleong 2002:3). According to Arikunto (2010:3) descriptive research is the study intended to investigate the situation, condition, circumstances, events, and other activities, and the result presented in the form of the research report.

The objects of this research was the English subtitled on the Korean drama entitled “I Hear Your Voice”, which limited on utterances in the English subtitle on the Korean drama entitled “I Hear Your Voice” including the declaration of illocutionary acts. The researcher took six episodes of eight teen episodes of the drama that are from 8th to 13th episode. The researcher took those episodes because on those episodes focused on one case that was indicated there were many declaration utterances. This research was held in November 13th to December 5th, 2013.

In this research the primary data source was taken from utterances found in the English subtitle on the video of the Korean drama entitled “I Hear Your Voice”. The data focused on the declaration of illocutionary acts. The video of this drama was downloaded from dramacrazy.eu in the internet. This drama was using Korean with running English subtitle. The running English

subtitle from this drama was the primary data in this research. The primary data was taken by transcribing the running English subtitle from the video which was downloaded from dramacrazy.eu, which was the web made especially for the Korean drama lovers around the world. In addition, the researcher used English drama script of “I Hear Your Voice” as secondary data to support the primary data.

The data are collected through some steps, they are observation, transcribing and documentation. The researcher did observation by watching the videos of the Korean drama entitled “I Hear Your Voice” to help find and select the declaration of illocutionary utterances. This method was used to help the researcher conduct this research as the supporting materials and data because the drama script that the researcher had was not complete. As a result, the researcher decided to support this research by doing observation to find the declaration utterances in this drama. The observation that the researcher did was watching the movie. After doing observation by watching the videos of drama I Hear Your Voice, the researcher transcribed the English subtitles of this drama. This activity was done to help the researcher conducting the written data as the primary data of this research. Transcription is process to encompass the talk, time, nonverbal actions, speaker and the hearer, the researcher transcribed the English subtitle from the Korean drama by determining the speaker, the hearer and the time. The writer typed the transcription in the table form consist of episode, time, name of the speaker and the dialogue. The researcher also held documentation by underline and highlight the utterances found in the transcription to find the variables that have been defined that is declaration utterances. If there is appears declaration utterances the researcher highlight or underline those utterances.

The data were analyzed by selecting and categorizing the utterance of declaration of illocutionary act found in the Korean drama “I Hear Your Voice”. The researcher selected the utterance in the Korean-English drama entitled “I Hear Your Voice” that includes declaration illocutionary acts. The researcher leaved out the other utterances. The researcher classified the utterance based on the forms of declaration of illocutionary act whether resigning, demising, christening, naming, excommunicating, appointing, sentencing, declaring war, and firing from employment.

DISCUSSION

The researcher analyzed the utterances in this drama which were performed by those people who have authorization to declare something which can change the world via their utterances. The judges, lawyers, prosecutions and police are people who have that authorization to do so, they can declare someone guilty or innocent, and declare someone became the suspect of the crime or witness. In this drama the researcher found many declaration utterances which were uttered by those institutional people such as sentencing, appointing, resigning, naming, and demising.

Type of Declaration Illocutionary Act

In the drama *I Hear Your Voice*, the researcher found many kinds of declaration utterances presented as well in the table below:

Table 2 Type of Declaration of Illocutionary Act

No	Type of Declaration	Number	Percentage
1.	Resigning	2	4,8 %
2.	Demising	3	7,3 %
3.	Naming	7	17,01 %
4.	Appointing	10	24,4 %
5.	Sentencing	19	46,3 %
Total		41	100%

The above table was presented the result of the data. It could be seen that there are 38 utterances of declaration of illocutionary act which divided into five categories. It was consist of 2 utterances of resigning, 3 utterances of demising, 7 utterances of naming, 8 utterances of appointing and the highest nominal of the declaration of illocutionary act was sentencing which was consist of 18 utterances.

1. Resigning

Resigning is expression used to declare someone resigns from their job. In this research the researcher found 2 utterances that belong to the types of declaration of illocutionary acts that is resigning. The researcher found in 9th and 14th episode of the drama.

Table 3 Resigning Declaration

No.	Episode	Time	Utterance
1.	9	00:38:07	Lawyer Jang: <i>“Attorney Cha gave up his position as a public defender.”</i>
2.	14	00:12:19	Lawyer Uhm: <i>“I can never be a lawyer in this circumstance. I can’t”</i>
Total:	2		

2. Demising

Demising is expression used to declare someone demis or death. In this research the researcher found 5 utterances that were the types of declaration of illocutionary act that is demising. The researcher found in 8th, 9th, 10th, and 12th episode of the drama.

Table 4 Demising declaration

No.	Code (Episode)	Time	Utterance
1.	8	00.00.11	Reporter: <i>“Around 11.00 last night, at a chicken restaurant Myeong Woldong, Seongmo city, a fire broke out from an known cause. The fire, after partially burning the restaurant, causing property damage which the fire department estimated at 5,4 million Won, was extinguished in 15 minute. In the accident, the 52 years old owner, Ms.Eo Choon Shim died.”</i>
2.	9	00:41:18	Reporter: <i>“Last night, around 9, at a fishing area in Yoen Ju, a left hand severed from a corpse was found so the police have started their investigation. Looking at the fingerprints on the hand, the owner of the hand is Mr. Min, who is on the wanted list.”</i>
3.	12	00:50:41	Directur Yang: <i>“Prosecutor, something big happened. The fruit store owner, Moon Seong Nam, who was called in for witness, in an accident yesterday night. she was dead.”</i>
Total:	3		

3. Naming

Naming is expression used to declare something name or naming something. In this research the researcher found 7 utterances that be one of the types of declaration illocutionary acts that is

naming. The researcher found in 9th, 10th, and 13th episode of the drama presented in the table below:

Table 5 Naming declaration

No.	Code (Episode)	Time	Utterance
1.	9	00:21:31	Police 2: “ <i>I think its smoke bomb. Like the ones used to kill the cockroaches.</i> ”
2.	10	00:05:54	Reporter: “Dismembered left hand found at fishery. Body seems to have been mutilated following the murder. Murder suspect of the “ <i>left hand</i> ” case_arrested. Took shelter for a year in a farming village.”
3.	10	00:25:10	Lawyer Cha Gwang Woo: “About Park Soo Ha’s case...how about we make this into a case of <i>Trial By Jury</i> ?”
4.	10	01:04:16	Lawyer Shin: ‘It’s going to the same way as Hwang Dal Jong’s case went 26 years ago. How despicable. <i>Even the case’s nickname is the same. The left-hand murdered case.</i> ”
5.	13	00:13:34	Lawyer Jang: “The case is <i>attempted murder for stabbing an assaultive husband.</i> ”
6.	13	00:13:51	Park Soo Ha : Hey, what’s with “ <i>bloody crap</i> ” while eating. “ <i>bloody crap</i> ”. You could just say that you’re going
7.	13	00:42:18	Park Soo Ha : Is it <i>dog food</i> again?
Total			7

4. Appointing

Appointing is expression used to declare someone accepted for a job. The researcher in this research found 8 utterances of declaration illocutionary act in episode 8th, 10th, 12th, and 13th. Those utterances were categorized into one of the types of declaration illocutionary act that was appointing. The data of appointing utterances presented in the table below:

Table 6 Appointing Declaration

No.	Code (Episode)	Time	Utterance
1.	8	00.01.04	Judge 2: “Has the suspect been charged with arson?” Judge 1: “Yes, did you know that <i>the case has been assigned to our court</i> ?” The Judges 1: “Exactly, why, of all places, does it have to be us? The incident was in Seongmo city.” The judges 3: “It seems this is jurisdiction of the defendant’s residence and the requested a transfer.”

2.	8	00.13.54	The Judge 1 “We don’t know yet if he killed her mother or not! We will know that only after the trial. I fully understand you’re in a difficult position. However, this is not a matter which you have the liberty of choice. For this kind of situation, public defenders are changed with exclusive responsibility. <i>And you’re that exclusive public defender, lawyer Cha.</i> ” Lawyer Cha: “Then, please change to lawyer Shin. I will personally request it of Lawyer Shin.” The Judges 1: “That would be difficult too”.
3.	8	00.14.22	Lawyer Cha: “why?” The Judges 1: “ <i>Min Joong Gook requested us to assign you as his lawyer</i> ”
4.	10	00:08:24	Lawyer Jang Hye Sung: “A public defender was requested. <i>I’m Park Soo Ha’s public defender.</i> So, I’m also going to the inspection of the scene.”
5.	10	00:13:44	Lawyer Jang Hye Sung: “Suddenly why are you being like this? <i>You’re the prosecutor of this case.</i> ”
6.	10	00:43:42	Prosecutor Seo Do Yeon: “ <i>I’m the public prosecutor for this case, Prosecutor Seo Do Yeon.</i> I stand here today to assist you to make judgment. In order to help you understand this case, I’ve prepare a presentation. (showing unusual presentation)”
7.	10	00:31:25	Lawyer Cha Gwang Woo: “Yes, <i>I was also assigned to Park Soo Ha’s case.</i> Since I don’t have an office, I’m going to borrow one here.”
8.	12	00:09:02	Lawyer Cha: “ <i>I’ll do it. Park Soo Ha’s lawyer. I said I’ll be his lawyer.</i> ”.
9.	13	00:28:19	Prosecutor Cho: “Prosecutor Seo, <i>Hwang Dal Choong’s case has been passed down to me</i> ”
10.	13	00:36:14	Jang Hye Sung: “ <i>So, you want Hwang Dal Choong’s case as a jury trial with me?</i> ”
Total:			10

5. Sentencing

Sentencing is an utterance that used to state that someone is to have a certain punishment. In this drama from chapter 8 to 13 the researcher found 17 sentencing declaration and 2 others from chapter 16 and 18. Those data of sentencing utterances presented in table below:

Table 7 Sentencing Declaration

No.	Code (Episode)	Time	Utterance
1.	8	00.23.44	Prosecutor Seo Do Yeon:

			<i>“Therefore, defendant Min Joon Gook is charged, under penal code article 250 pursuant to section 64, with Arson and Homicide by Arson.”</i>
2.	8	00:38:38	<p>Lawyer Shin :” So, you’re going out? As a witness on the Min Joon Gook case? “Tiffany”</p> <p>Hwang Dal Joong :” <i>Yes, at the next court session, I’m going out as a witness.</i>” (00:38:44)</p> <p>Lawyer Shin :” Why are you going out as a witness? For the prosecution’s side? Didn’t you said that Min Joon Gook was a good person?”</p>
3.	9	00:09:19	<p>The judges 1:</p> <p>“Defendant Min Joong kook was indicted for murder as follows : on June,9,2012in Myeongwondong, Sangmoo city at Eo Choon Shim’s chicken restaurant, he struck the victim with a blunt instrument rendering her unconsciousness. After which, he started the fire to camouflage it as an accident. Therefore, he would have acted differently if he had really wanted to murder. So, there is enough doubt to mitigate the charges against the defendant. According to the law, if there is reasonable doubt of the guilt, then the court must find the defendant innocent. The fundamental principle in criminal procedure being that decision must be made in favor of the defendant. <i>Therefore, per Law of Court, section 325, the defendant is acquitted.</i>”</p>
4.	9	00:38:07	<p>Lawyer Jang Hye Sung:</p> <p><i>“Min Joong Kook has been charged for attempted murderer and retaliation.”</i></p>
5.	9	00:42:08	<p>Lawyer Jang: “I’m Jang Hye Sung, a public defender. I’m Park Soo Ha’s guardian.”</p> <p>Police: <i>“You should have been a proper guardian. He killed a person.” If we have that much evidence, it doesn’t make sense that the criminal is Park Soo Ha?</i> (00:42:26)</p>
6.	10	00:01:24	<p>Police: “I can’t. He confessed that he killed him with his own hands. How can I let go a criminal? He might be pretending to have lost his memory. <i>We’ll do this according to the law. We’ll file for an arrest warrant, and when it is issued, he will be detained unconditionally.</i>”</p> <p>(00:01:50)</p>
7.	10	00:11:19	<p>Lawyer Jang Hye Sung: “Don’t take of the masked, please! <i>He’s still in the position of an accused.</i>”</p>
8.	10	00:44:18	<p>Prosecutor Seo Do Yeon: <i>“In this case the victim, Min Joon Kook, murdered the father’s defendant Park Soo Ha 11 years ago. Even after Min Joon Kook was released from jail, he stalked the defendant and last year, he injured the defendant. The defendant, bearing a grudge against the victim, around at</i></p>

			23:00 hours on July,22 nd , 2012, met the victim at Big Fish Fishery in Yeon Joo City and killed him. And, he dismembered the body, it is believed that he hid the body parts in the river.”
9.	10	00:45:24	Prosecutor Seo Do Yeon: “ <i>In accordance with article 250 and 161 of the Criminal Law, the prosecution is charging the murder, destruction and mutilation of the corpse, and concealment of the body.</i> ”
10.	10	01:04:45	Lawyer Cha: “ <i>Yes, there is one suspect that matches up with all the evidence. Min Joon Kook.</i> ”
11.	11	00:06:36	The judge 1: “ <i>Finally, in regard to this case’s charge, we cannot view that there is no evidence beyond reasonable doubt, and in this situation, when doubtful, following the great principle of criminals suits that defendant’s there’s no choice but judge so. As such, in accordance with latter part of the criminal code 325, the defendant... is not guilty.</i> ”
12.	12	00:12:24	Hwang Dal Jong: “ <i>Thank you. If it wasn’t for you, Lawyer Shin, I wouldn’t even have anyone to sign me out.</i> ”
13.	12	00:08:17	Prosecutor Seo: “ <i>Because we weren’t looking for him. As of now, we have to start looking for him. Director Yang. Send Moon Suk Nam a letter summoning her as a witness</i> ”
14.	12	00:51:43	Prosecutor Seo: “ <i>Starting from now, we are stating that Min Joon Kook is alive. Get Min Joon Kook on the wanted list.</i> ”
15.	13	00:01:41	Lawyer Jang Hye Sung: “ <i>Hey, you stupid. That’s a later problem. Seo Do Yeon said she won’t look into your case any further. So, you are not a defendant,</i> ”
16.	13	00:11:01	Detective Kang : “ <i>What’s wrong with Hwang Dal Choong? As soon as he was released he stabbed a person, and now he’s come looking for you</i> ”
17.	13	00:23:32	Prosecutor Seo: “ <i>Criminal Code Article 250 Paragraph 1 is applicable. Under the provisions of Article 250, the Defendant is charged with attempted murder.</i> ”
18.	16	00:03:06	Judge 1: “ <i>we will start the verdict for the case 2013 1354 Hwang Dal Joong. The result of the jury verdict deviates from existing jurisprudence and our opinion, it cannot be said that it is completely incorrect. As such, in accordance with the Criminal Law 328-1-1, the prosecution is dismissed.</i> ”
19.	18	00:56:55	Judge 1: “ <i>all the crimes he has committed was for revenge, to cover up those crimes, he has killed innocent people. He cover it up by making it look like an accident with his extremely cruel ways. However, the victim Doctor Woo forged the documents making the reason the defendant’s wife die. The defendant Life sentence</i> ”
Total:			19

CONCLUSION

After analyzing the data of declaration of illocutionary act, the researcher accomplished to the conclusion as follows:

- a. In the Korean-English drama “I Hear Your Voice”, in episode 8 to 13 found 40 utterances of declaration of illocutionary act. Those utterances classified into five categories that are resigning, demising, naming, appointing and sentencing. From 40 declaration utterances were found there are 2 utterances of resigning it was 5% from 100% total, 12,5% consist of 5 utterances of demising, 17,5% consist 7 utterances of naming, 20% consist of 8 utterances of appointing and 45% consist of 18 utterances of sentencing.
- b. The result of this research can be implicated on the English Language Teaching. The teachers can use this research as an authentic material to teach Pragmatic especially about Speech Acts. In addition, the result of this research able to used to teach about the expressions. Those are expression of *resigning, demising, naming, appointing, and sentencing*.

After analyzing the data and discussing the result, the researcher give some suggestions as follows:

- a. English Teacher

The researcher hopes the English teacher can use this study as the authentic material to teach speech act.

- b. English Department Students

The researcher hope this research could be one of references in studying speech act especially to give more understanding about declaration illocutionary act as one of the part of illocutionary categories by Searle.

- c. The future researcher

This research could be one of the references in studying speech acts and for the other researcher, the researcher advice to use the title or topic, but which has not been conducted yet, such as types of locutionary acts, types of perlocutionary acts, or other types of illocutionary acts.

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Co-occurrences of *Kok* and other Markers in Colloquial Jakartan Indonesian

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes discourse marker (DM) kok (why) in colloquial Jakartan Indonesian. Co-occurrences of markers are noticeable features. It focuses on examining the emotive and textual functions of the co-occurrences of kok and other markers. This study applied corpus methods. It was found that there are 7 markers co-occur with kok namely lho, eh, oh, lha, wah, ah, and ih that always appear on the left side of kok. Only DM sih occurs on the right side. In emotive functions, the co-occurrences were used to show shock, disappointment, and disgust. Three markers might occur together in one utterance which cause more complex senses. Some utterances with kok appear repeatedly in the form of questions. It seems that in questions with kok, the speakers feel more curious and demand more responses. In textual functions, the speakers use the co-occurrences to raise a topic, emphasize, demand answers, and negotiate. Moreover, it was also used when the speakers have just noticed something and tried to make the interlocutors notice.

Keywords: discourse marker, co-occurrence, emotive function, textual function

INTRODUCTION

Indonesian is a national language of Indonesia which is an archipelago that has many local languages. As a national language in such country, Indonesian has some local variations. One of the variations is colloquial Jakartan Indonesian. This variety is spoken in Jakarta, the capital city of Indonesia. As the capital city, people with different local languages come to Jakarta. The Jakartan Indonesian might be influenced by the local languages. The influences

can be in the aspects related to discourse. In colloquial language, discourse marker (DM) is a feature that distinguishes colloquial language from formal spoken language and written language. Its meanings, moreover, might change from one situation to the other ones (Aijmer, 2014). Therefore, studying the utterances in dialogues to see the context is necessary.

DM is a part of pragmatic marker. DMs occur to create meaning as a whole by joining several elements in discourse. They are used by the participants in discourse to make the optimum sense of their utterances are delivered (Schiffrin, 2003). They, moreover, guide the listeners to make interpretation based on the message they heard (Han, 2011; Schiffrin, 2003).

Fraser (1996, p. 169) mentioned that DM is a type of pragmatic marker that “signals the relationship of the basic message to the foregoing discourse.” According to Biber, Johansson, Conrad, & Finegan (1999, p.1046) it is “loosely attached to the clause and connected with ongoing interaction.” As it carries discourse functions, it represents how the speakers manage the discourse in conversation in order to deliver and understand meanings. It is also defined as “a syntactically heterogeneous class of expressions which are distinguished by their function in discourse and the kind of meaning they encode” (Blakemore, 2004, p.221). From all definitions, it can be seen that DMs contribute to meaning making.

Some studies focused on the functions of DMs. Wang (2011) studied DMs *ano* in Japanese and *nage* in mandarin Chinese. They function to develop close relationship among speakers. The DMs are used as a politeness strategy in which the speakers reduced the potency of his own or interlocutor’s faces threatening acts. It is a part of speakers’ ways to show emotions with considering the effects to the interlocutors. In addition, they were also used when the speakers found sameness with their interlocutors. Furthermore, they give color to the nature of conversation. Fischer in Schiffrin (1987) mentioned they influence turn taking system and the flow of information in conversation. DMs do not only affect the coherency of discourse but also influence the relationship among the speakers (Furman & Özyürek, 2007). They might occur in transition. Besides, they appear to show how speakers and hearers involved in the message (Biber, et al., 1999).

As carrying emotive functions, DMs show stance (Aijmer, 2014; Han, 2011; Hiramoto, 2012). According to Biber & Conrad (2003), stance carries feelings and assessment. Thus, the speakers try to make others understand what they feel and think about even though they do not directly use content words to express feelings.

Textual functions mean how DMs are applied to organize texts such as in making the listeners pay attention to the messages that are going to deliver, marking structure of the texts, setting up boundary, and switching topics (Aijmer & Rühlemann, 2015). DMs are used to make coherence in discourse (Schiffrin, 1992). They are applied to make the texts make sense and easily to be understood.

The study of DMs in Catalan and Spanish has similarity to the present study (Cuenca and Marin, 2009). It discussed the co-occurrences of two markers. However, the term co-occurrence in this study is different from the one in the present study. It refers to two or more words occur as a chunk in Cuenca and Marin's study while, in the present study, it was used to define as a word(s) that occur together within the span of four words to the left and right. The previous study explored the functional category of discourse markers and distributional properties. It was found that two or more markers might co-occur.

Sneddon (2006) also studied DMs in colloquial Jakartan Indonesia. The DMs are *deh, dong, kan, kek, kok, loh, mah, masa, nah, nih, tuh, sih, ya/yah, and yuk*. The discussion of the co-occurrences in Sneddon's work is limited. It only gives some examples of what DMs co-occur with other DMs. According to him, the function of co-occurrences is to build connection among speakers in conversation. Most examples given in his work were not given in wider chunk of dialogue. Furthermore, the context of the utterances must be considered. It did not consider how the co-occurrences carry functions particularly textual and emotive functions. Besides, the co-occurrences that were investigated are only the DM and DM. Co-occurrences to other markers such as interjections have not been studied. The present study gives contribution on the study of co-occurrences of DM *kok* and other markers (DMs and interjections) especially in their textual and emotive functions.

One of the DMs in colloquial Jakartan Indonesia is *kok*. *Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia* (KBBI) which is an Indonesian-Indonesian dictionary published by the government gives two definitions for *kok*. The first one is as a word that functions to emphasize and strengthen speaker's intention. The second one, it is a synonym of *mengapa* and *kenapa* (why). As a synonym of *mengapa* and *kenapa*, when the speakers use *kok*, they ask for

reasons from other participants in the dialogue. They expect explanation to answer their questions.

Schiffrin (2003) mentioned that DMs have cognitive, expressive, textual, and social functions in a discourse. From DMs, speakers' thought and emotion that are not delivered directly by using content words can be realized. Moreover, it gives views on how the speakers construct dialogue in such a way to deliver their ideas. The speakers also consider their relationship with the listeners and tried to manage it in social interaction. For the case of *kok*, it was found that *kok* tends to occur with other markers in utterances. As we have shown before, the position of the other markers can be on the left or right side of *kok*. In addition, their co-occurrences tend to be with other markers that carries exclamation in meaning such as *wah* (Anonymous, 2017). Words that carry exclamation are called as interjections such as oh, yeah, and wow. Interjection is a type of pragmatic marker (Aijmer, 2014). Like DM, its occurrences can be structurally independent. In addition, they carry speakers' emotions (Biber, et al., 1999; Fraser, 1996; Neal, 2014;). Neal (2014, p. 251) stated they "connect utterances to foregoing talk, they act as tags, they fill pause, they signal listener responses, and assessments, all in addition to expressing strong emotion." Oh shows speakers' participation in discourse. By producing oh they sign they receive information. Furthermore, oh that occurs in the question demands more detailed information from the ones that gave the information (Schiffrin, 1993). Thus, it plays roles in creating the texts and showing emotions. The findings are much related to the textual and emotive functions.

For the case emotive function, the nature of DMs and interjections enable them to do so. Besides, it seems that the construction of co-occurrences of *kok* and other markers carries functions related to the way the speakers construct the dialogues. It is about the textual function of DMs. Intriguing by the findings, this study sought to answer the research questions as follows: 1). What are the emotive functions of the co-occurrences of *kok* and other discourse markers? 2). What are the textual functions of the co-occurrences of *kok* and other discourse markers?

RESEARCH METHOD

The present study applies corpus methods in discourse analysis. In doing so, quantitative considerations are counted. It produced results that give description and explain phenomena that is investigated in discourse (Partington in Thornbury, 2010). The use of

corpus study to analyze DMs is recognized as an effective way because DMs are lexis that can be obtained easily by using the corpus tool. Lists of concordance lines of DMs can be provided. Furthermore, it can shed light on how speakers use DMs in order to optimize the sense of the message to be understood by the listeners (Rühlemann, 2010). This study is limited only to emotive and textual functions and these functions are possible to be examined by a corpus method. As a study that applied corpus methods, first, the corpus was built by compiling the data from CHILDES (Child Language Data Exchange System). The size of the corpus is around 370,000 words. Next, the collocates of *kok* were investigated. Based on the wordlist of the collocates, the words that belong to DMs were selected. Close examination of the concordance lines was conducted to see the textual and emotive functions of the co-occurrences.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

It was found that markers on the left side of *kok* are *lho*, *eh*, *oh*, *lha*, *wah*, *ah*, and *ih*. On the right side, there is only *sih*. Only *lho* and *sih* that belong to the classification of DMs of colloquial Jakartan Indonesian by Sneddon (2006). *Lha* was not included in the classification. However, it is considered to be a DM in this study because its function and meaning almost similar to *lho*. The DMs, therefore, are *lho*, *lha*, and *sih* while the interjections are *eh*, *oh*, *wah*, *ah*, and *ih*. Their co-occurrences with *kok* carry the sense of exclamation. The co-occurrences occur in statements and questions. All of them function to show that the speakers feel shocked and surprised.

Lho and Kok

In this co-occurrence, *kok* appear in the questions. They can appear as chunks. Furthermore, they can be separated by some words such as in *lho itu bekas jeruk kok* and *lho dia kok*. *Lho* functions to show surprise (Sneddon, 2006). When *lho* and *kok* co-occur, it makes the speakers asked for reasons with surprise. In addition, the speaker used it when he negotiated his idea in order not do particular action.

- (1) A: Burungnya kan kesian ditembak
bird kan pittty shot

- B: (B)urung apa?
bird what
- A: Kalo yang terbang, jangan ditembak, kesian
If which fly don't shot pitty
- B: (B)urung, (b)ur(ung), (ger)eja
bird bird church
- A: Burung, burung gereja jangan ditembak, kesian
bird bird church don't shot pitty
- B: Tembak aja
shoot just
- A: *lho, kok* ditembak?
DM DM shot
- B: Galak tapi
fierce but
- A: It's pitty to shot the bird.
- B: Which bird?
- A: If the bird is flying, don't shoot, it's pitty.
- B: Sparrow.
- A: But fierce.
- A: Don't shoot sparrows. It's pitty.
- B: Just shoot.
- A: How come it was shot?
- B: It's fierce.

A felt shock because he requested B not to shot from the beginning. He produced two imperative utterances that requested B not to shot the bird. He also gave reason why he made such instruction. Nevertheless, B still kept his intention to shot. Through the question *lho, kok, ditembak*, A wonder why B persisted to do the action.

In another case, *lho kok* occurs as one phrase in one utterance. In the dialog below, the participants are a child and an adult. The adult is called as *om* (uncle).

- (2) A: Om Okki, Om Okki, ambil sendok dong!
uncle O uncle O take spoon DM
- B: Ya, ambil sendiri dong, tuh.

DM take alone DM DM

A: Aaah.

Exc

B: Lho kok?

DM DM

A: Uncle Okki, Uncle Okki, please take a spoon for me.

B: Please, do it by yourself.

A: Ah.

B: How come?

Through *lho kok*, B questioned A's response to his instruction. Like in the first dialogue given as the example, the speakers that produced *lho kok* made imperative utterance before he produced *lho kok*. In this dialogue, it can be seen when the speaker said *ya, ambil sendiri, dong*. The sense in the dialogue tends to be imperative.

Lho kok is not only a response to an utterance but it can be a response to an action that was seen by the speaker as in the following dialogue.

(3) A: Oke deh, maen cukur-cukuran deh.

okay DM play shave DM

B: Kompornya beresin ya?

stove tidy.up DM

C: Eh, liat!

Exc look

B: Lho, kok digunting?

DM DM cut

A: Okay, let's play, pretend we do shaving.

B: Should we tidy up the stove?

A: Hey, look.

B: How come did you cut it?

Speaker C asked other participants in the conversation to look at him. After that, B questioned about it by saying *lho, kok digunting?* It is not only language produced but also

the sudden actions done by the other participant that created situation in which B shows shock.

Feeling of shock in speaker's question can be accompanied by the feeling of disappointment as can be seen in the following dialogue.

- (4) A: Lho, kok rumahnya kosong?
 DM DM house-nya empty
 B: Rumahnya mau dimasuki oleh binatang.
 house will enter by animal
 A: Yah, kosong.
 DM empty
 A: How come was the house was empty?
 B: The house will be entered by animals.
 A: Oh no. Empty.

B gives a reason to A's question. After hearing it, A mentioned again the emptiness of the house with disappointing tone.

Lho kok might occur in sequences showing how intriguing the phenomenon for the speaker. A produced *lho kok* twice in one speaking turn. By doing this, A has questions in his mind. As a response, B does not give reason to answer A's question. He gives other information that might be helpful to answer A's questions.

- (5) A: Lho, kok, cuman begini? Lho, kok, ngga ada ininya?
 DM DM only like.this DM DM not be this-nya?
 B: Tapi ini ada pelurunya, Tante.
 but this be bullet-nya aunt
 A: How come it is just like this? How come it is missing?
 B: But it has the bullet, Aunt.

In another dialogue, the sequences of *lho kok* was produced by both speakers. A repeated *lho kok* two times in his first utterance. Then, A and B produced one question with *lho kok*. From the utterance *lho kok*, the speakers said that that it should not be like this.

- (6) A: Lho... Lho kok ada tiga? Lho, kok ada empat?
 DM DM DM be three DM DM be four
 B. Lho, kok banyak?
 DM DM many

A: Lho, kok ada empat?

DM DM be four

B: Tu, dua, ...

one two

A: How come there are three things? How come there are four things?

B: How come there are many?

A: How come there are four?

B: One, two,

None of the speakers answered the dialogue. They only questioned. It seems that the questioning sense is stronger in this dialogue.

In the other dialogue, *lho kok* occurs with *wah* which is an interjection. It forms *wah lho kok*. After asking for the reason, speaker A asked the person that did it. Then, he questioned the reason again. In this question, he did not produce *wah* and *loh*. *Kok* occurs without any markers because the speaker was not as shocked as when he produced the first question. In the first utterance, he produced three questions. The first and the last questions talk about the same issue.

(7) A: Wah, lho, kok miring ni?

DM DM DM slanting this

A: Siapa sih yang mutusin, kok miring?

who DM which break DM slanting

B: Oh, karena dimasukin ke kardus.

DM because put into box

A: Wow. How come it is slanting? Who broke it? How come it was slanting?

B: Oh, because it was put into the box.

Three questions that occur in one speaking turn show that it makes the tone of the dialogue becomes more questioning. The participant observed the object and it led him to produce questions related to the objects.

Eh and Kok

Co-occurrences of *eh* and *kok* can be in a statement or question. In the following example, it occurs in a question. They discussed about the train such as experience and where the train is. Then, B asked questioned. He asked the question which begins with *eh ... kok*. *Eh ... kok* shows that he just noticed new thing. He made it as the topic that he would discuss and tried to make the others notice. Through his question, speaker A raised new topic about the train. In this question, he used the word *tapi* (but) which shows contrast. He contrasted what he found about the train that the train does not move with his concept that the train should move.

- (8) A: Kereta api. Ya kan Om Oki.
 Train DM DM uncle O
- B: Iya, bener, kok tau, Mamas? Emang pernah ...?
 yes right how come know M actually ever
- C: Kan ...
 DM
- A: Pernah naik
 ever take
- C: Kalo kalo ...
 if if
- A: Pernah liat kok
 ever see DM
- C: Kalo
 if
- A: Di stasiun
 at train.station
- B: Eh, tapi kok ngga bisa jalan ya?
 Exc but DM not can work DM
- D: Eeh.
 Exc.
- A: Train. Is it right, Uncle Oki?
- B. Yes, that's right. How come you know it, Mamas? Actually ... ?
- C: Yeah
- A: I took it

C: If , if

A: I saw it, you know.

C: If

A: At the train station.

B: Anyway, but how come it cannot work?

D: Yeah.

Eh and *kok* also occurs in a statement. As a statement, the function of *kok* is to emphasize. Therefore, it makes others notice particular facts that would be said by the speaker. It can be said as speaker's way to emphasize his utterance. A complained about his aunt that did not want to help. As a response to this complain, C (aunt) made A realized why she did it.

(9) A: Cepet, cepet. Masuk rumah semua! Masuk rumah! Masuk rumah!

hurry hurry come house all come house come house

B: Ayo cepet.

come on hurry

A: Wa, tante! Bantuin dong! Aah, tante nih nggak mau bantuin.

Exc aunt help DM DM aunt DM not want help

C: Eh, yang maen kamu kok.

DM which play you DM

A: Hurry, hurry. Come to the house, all. Come to the house. Come to the house.

B: Come on. Hurry.

A: Aunt, please help. Ah, aunt is not willing to help.

C: Hey, it is you that play.

Oh* and *Kok

The co-occurrences can be seen in the form of questions and statements. In the example below, the co-occurrence is in the question. *Oh* is closed to the information given in discourse.

(10) A: Tante, ni sosis sisanya dari sekolah.

Aunt this sausage rest-nya from school

B: Oh, kok enggak dimakan di sekolah?
 oh how come not eat at school

A: Satu udah dimakan di sekolah.
 one already eat at school

A: Aunt, here is/are (a) leftover sausage(s) from the school.

B: Oh, how come you didn't eat it at the school?

A: I ate it one at the school.

B gave response to the information given by A. When the speaker used *oh*, she just knew the information because the speaker told her. *Oh* also functions to notice that the speaker paid attention to the interlocutor. It is in line with the functions of *oh* mentioned by Schirffrin (1993). Based on the information given, B asked a question using *kok*. A did not directly give the reason. He added another information that can be used by B to guess.

As a statement, *oh* and *kok* occurs in the following dialogue. *Oh* is a response to B question. However, the response was not given directly after the question. There is an utterance produced by A before A answered the question. In this dialogue, speaker A did some actions. She was able to answer the question after doing this action. *Oh ... kok* in the following example shows that the speaker has just known particular fact and emphasize the fact.

(11) A: Tante, Bety mo pipis dulu ya.
 aunt B want pee early DM

B: Oh iya. Bisa nggak pipis sendiri?
 oh yes can not pee alone

A: Ah, ininya dilepas.
 Ex this free

C: Yah.

DM

A: Oh bisa kok itu.
 oh can DM that

A: Aunt, Bety wants to pee first.

B: Yes. Can you pee alone?

A: Ah, it should be opened.

C: Oh, no.

A: Oh, it worked, you know.

Lha and Kok

A shows his wonder by using *lha kok*. Instead of giving reason to A, he asked a question too. A asked again but in this question, he did not use *lha*. This case is similar to the co-occurrences of *lho* and *kok*. *Lha* did not appear because it is not the first time for him to know it. In the first question, it was the first time for her to realize the fact. Then, he questioned it with *lha kok*. In the second question, speaker C gave explanation as a response.

- (12) A: Lha kok ada kacang?
 DM DM there peanut
 C: Yang satu lagi mana?
 which one again where
 A: Kok ada kacang?
 DM there peanut
 B: Mana? Ya udah tambahin kacang juga nggak pa pa, enak.
 which okay add peanut also not.problem yummy
 A: What. How come there are peanuts?
 C: Where is the other one?
 A: How come there are peanuts?
 B: Which one? Okay. It's not a problem to add peanuts. Yummy.

In another dialogue, the speaker produced two questions in one utterance. In the first question, *lha* occurs with *kok*. However, in the second question, it occurs without *lha*. This is still in line with the case in the previous dialogue where the speakers produced two questions with *kok*. *Kok* occurs with *lha* in the first question. However, it appears without any other DM in the second one.

- (13) A: Lha kok gambar semua ni?
 DM DM picture all this
 A: Ni kok nggak ada gambarnya kayak ini?
 this DM not be picture like this
 B: Oh, nggak ada. Ini juga nggak ada.

oh not there this also not there

A: What. How come all are pictures? How come it doesn't have a picture like this?

B: There aren't any. This one also doesn't have.

B did not give reasons. He only emphasized the point that A mentioned. He also made the last statement to show that the same case also happens.

In the dialogue below, A produced question with *kok* based on his observation. Then, B gave a response. A asked another question with a different topic. In this question, *kok* occurs with *lha*.

- (14) A: Eh, bikin setan aja deh.
Exc make devil just DM
- B: Bikin setan?
make devil
- C: (S)etan di hutan, kalo malem-malem.
devil at forest if night
- B: Ni malem-malem ni ceritanya.
this night this story-nya
- A: Iya. Kok begitu sih?
yes DM like.that DM
- B: Nanti dulu, belum jadi.
later before not.yet become
- A: Lha kok, eee, setannya terbang?
DM DM exc devil-nya fly
- B: Terbang.
Fly
- A: Hey. Let's just make devil.
- B: Make devil?
- C: Devil is at the forest at night.
- B: Let's say it is night.
- A: How come it is like this.
- B: Later. It hasn't been finished.
- A: How come devil flies.
- B: Fly.

The case here is different from the case previously discussed. In this case, *kok* without DM occurs first. It happens differently because in this case, the speaker asked for two different things.

Wah and Kok

Kok that occurs with *wah* gives sense of wonder. *Wah ... kok* is an expression of wonder of what C saw. It triggered his curiosity that led him to produce a question with *kok*. There is no response towards C's question. A switched the topic. Then, C gave a response to a new topic.

- (15) A: Ni Mamas bikin anjing.
 this Mamas make dog
- B: Tuh.
 that
- C: He em.
 DM
- A: Setan
 devil
- C: Wah, setannya kok kayak cacing?
 Exc devil-nya DM like worm
- A: Ini rumputnya.
 this grass-nya
- C: Apa tuh, rumput, Mas?
 what that grass M
- A: Now, Mamas is making a dog.
- B: That one.
- C: Yes.
- A: Devil
- C: Wow. How come the devil is like a worm?

A: This is the grass.

B: What is it? Is it grass, Mas?

In another dialog, there are two questions in a speaking turn. It is only the second question that used *kok*. Even though the first question did not use *kok* (*ini mana ini?*), the sense of questioning is still strong in the utterance that creates the nuance of questioning in the dialogue.

(16) A: Ini mana ini? Wah, ini kok copot?
 this which this DM this how.come detached

B: Harus dua tapi, nggak boleh.
 must two but not can

A: Where is it? Wow, how come it is detached?

B: But, it must be two. It can't be.

In this case, there is no reason given to answer A's question.

Ih and Kok

When *ih* occurs with *kok*, there is a sense of questioning with negative feeling that makes the speaker felt horrific. In the following dialogue, the negative feeling is dirty because the hair should not be there.

(17) A: Tuh ada tissue.
 that there tissue

B: Heh?

What

A: Pake tissue, ya?
 use tissue DM

C: Ih, kok ada rambut sih?
 Exc how.come be hair DM

A: That is a tissue.

B: Eh?

A: Use a tissue, don't you?

C: How come the hair is there?

In the other case, the negative feeling is shame. A did self-talking in which he asked a question and express what he felt. The other speakers did not give a response. B talked about new topic. Then, C responded to this new topic.

- (18) A: Ih, ce(lana), celananya kok gitu?
 DM pants-nya pants-nya how.come like.that?
 A: Ih, malu. Om Okki malu.
 DM ashamed Uncle O ashamed.
 B: Diminum, Mas Okki.
 drink Mas Okki
 C. Iya, Bu.
 yes ma'am
 A: Yuck. The pants. How come the pants like that? Yuck. Uncle Okki, I am ashamed.
 B: Have a drink, Mas Okki.
 C: Yes, Ma'am.

Sih and Kok

Sih is the only DM that occurs on the right side of *kok*. In the questions, *sih* plays a role to make the dialogue smooth and emphasize the focus of questions (Sneddon, 2006). *Kok* can occur in the beginning of the sentence after the addressing term. In the following example, *kok* occur after the addressing term, *ma*. *Ma* means *mama* (mother).

- (19) A: Ma, kok nggak ada kulitnya sih?
 Ma how.come not be skin-nya DM
 B: Kulitnya susah dong.
 skin-nya hard DM
 A: Ma, how come it doesn't have a skin.
 B: The skin is hard.

In the dialogue above, A asked her mother, a person that must be respected based on local culture. Based on participants' relationship, A tried to smooth the question by using *sih*. The question used *kok* which demand an explanation. To make it less demanding, the speaker used *sih*.

In another case, *kok* occurs in the middle of the sentence. B responded by mentioning the issue that was mentioned by speaker A before he gave the reason.

- (20) A: Si Atan kok nggak keliatan sih?

dim Atan how.come not seen DM
 B: Nggak keliatan, Atan di bawah.
 not see Atan at under

A: How come I didn't see Atan?

B: I didn't see him. Atan is on the ground below.

The co-occurrences of *sih* and *kok* in the two dialogues above emphasize the focus of the questions to the listeners. By doing so, the speakers directed the listener to get the focus of the questions. Thus, the listeners would give more relevant information to answer the questions. It is in line with what was mentioned by Han (2011) that DMs are intended by the speakers to make the listeners interpret the messages correctly.

CONCLUSION

In terms of emotive functions, the co-occurrences carry the expressions of shock and surprise. It is also possible that expressions of disappointment and horrific gives nuance to the dialogue. The speakers concern towards particular issues and have curiosity about the issues. It led them to make questions with the co-occurrences of *kok* and other markers. Two questions with *kok* might be produced in one utterance. One of them might carry co-occurrences of *kok* and other markers whereas the other one has only *kok*. In terms of textual functions, the co-occurrences play roles to address new topics, show information that is taken and given, make the other participants notice about particular issues, and smooth the dialogues.

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Maxim of Cooperative Principle Violation by Dodit Mulyanto in Stand-up Comedy Indonesia Season 4

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on cooperative principle violation done by Dodit Mulyanto in Stand Up Comedy Indonesia season 4 using Grice's theory. Grice expressed cooperative principle to suggest that in conversational interaction people work on the assumption that a certain set of rules is in operation, unless they receive indications to the contrary. The aims of this research are to classify the maxims of cooperative principle and to explain how Dodit Mulyanto violates cooperative principle to raise humor in Stand Up Comedy Indonesia season 4. Besides, this research is also directed to discover the types of violation maxims, the most dominant violation maxim, and to explain the causes of the most dominant violation maxim in Dodit Mulyanto's Stand Up Comedy Indonesia season 4. This research is conducted using qualitative method. The sources of data are the 17 videos of Dodit Mulyanto's speech during his performance in Stand Up Comedy Indonesia Kompas TV season 4 by downloading from YouTube site. The data are the utterances of Dodit Mulyanto which considered contain the violation of cooperative principles. The data are collected using the check list instrument and then analyzed based on the violation on each maxim. At the end, the researcher draws the conclusion which is in accordance with the research finding. The results of the analysis shows that all types of maxim were violated; 12 utterances violation maxim of quantity (24,4%), 13 utterances violation maxim of quality (26,5%), 22 utterances violation maxim of relation (44,9%), and 2 utterances violation maxim of manner (4,1%). The most dominant type of violation

maxims was the violation maxim of relation because Dodit Mulyanto delivered too much message, which is unmatched with the topic or changed conversation topic abruptly or did the wrong causality, than is required to raise humor in Stand Up Comedy Indonesia Kompas TV season 4.

Keywords: *Cooperative Principle, Maxim Violation, Stand Up Comedy.*

INTRODUCTION

The language used in daily life is a unique, arbitrary, and conventional sign system / emblem / speech sound which is used by the public in order to communicate each other. According to Longman Advanced American Dictionary (2007, p. 895), language is a system of communication by written or spoken words which is used by the people of a particular country or area. The language built from the habits and the geographical area where the speakers are living. Good language developed based on a certain system and a set of rules were observed by the speakers.

Originally, the function of language is as a communication tool (Bühler (1934) in Diessel, 2014, p.3). Hence, the language has more specialized function that is for establishing relationships, solidarity, and cooperation within the community, the language had been used to express mind with the feeling so that the listener will able to sense what is discussed about. As a communication tool, the language is used to convey the ideas, feeling, whether real or imagination. The imagination function is usually in the form of art works, including poetry, stories, fairy tales, and jokes. In the jokes, language is used as a communication tool by violating maxims of communication, they are cooperative principle and politeness principle maxim.

The linguistics which examines the violations of maxims in communication is pragmatic. Pragmatics is the study of language from the point of view of users, especially of the choices they make, the constrain they encounter in using language in social interaction and the effect their use of language has on other participant in the act of communication (Crystal

1985 in Kasper 1997). It is clear that pragmatics is the study about relation between language and context that are used in community.

The violation of cooperative maxims commonly used in creating humor. The utterances that made by Stand Up comedian (comic) in Stand Up Comedy Indonesia (SUCI) event on Kompas TV –in this case Dodit Mulyanto- shaping a discourse based on a predetermined theme. The discourse is about the problems in society and attractively packaged in humor and tends to give the information in the form of persuasive discourse to the viewers of Stand up Comedy to provide a solution to these problems.

Indeed, after the writer, watched the Stand Up Comedy season 4 show, he found some phenomena that make him interested in knowing more about the language of humor used by Dodit Mulyanto in Stand Up Comedy Indonesia season 4 through pragmatic study and to find out how Dodit uses the language to raise the humor on his show at Stand Up Comedy Indonesia Kompas TV.

The research questions of the present study are what the maxims of cooperative principle which are violated by Dodit Mulyanto in Stand Up Comedy Indonesia season 4 in order to raise humor and how does Dodit violate cooperative principle to raise humor in Stand Up Comedy Indonesia season 4.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter discusses some related literature that consists of the definition of pragmatics, the theory of cooperative principle, the theory of politeness principle, and the definition of maxim violation.

Pragmatics

There are some definitions about pragmatics that can help us to understand it deeply. Grundy (2000, p.3) states: “Pragmatics is about explaining how we produce and understand such every day, but apparently rather peculiar uses of language.” It means that pragmatics, the study explains us how to produce utterances and comprehend what people say in daily conversation although maybe they use unfamiliar language.

Leech (1983, p.11) explains that general pragmatics is abstraction between the study of language in total abstraction from the situation, and the study of more socially specialized uses of language. Hence, it is clear that pragmatics is the study about the relation between language and context that are used in the community.

Levinson (1983, p.9) gives a definition that pragmatics is the study of those relations between language and context that are grammaticalized, or encoded in the structure of a language. This means pragmatics has relation with grammar because what we will say must grammatically correct. Thus, this study cause us learn how to make utterances that are right in grammar and the hearer can interpret the meaning. Besides, pragmatics is a systematic way of explaining the language use in context. It seeks to explain aspects of meaning which cannot be found in the plain sense of words or structures, as explained by semantics.(Moore, 2003).

From the definitions above, it can be concluded that pragmatics is a field linguistics study which does not only explain about language but also explain how to produce and understand the language use in our real life following the factors that influence the language choice. It teaches us how to apply it in our daily life.

Pragmatics is relevant with politeness because politeness is a strategy (or series of strategies) employed by a speaker to achieve a variety of goals, such as promoting or maintaining harmonious relations (Thomas, 1995, p.157). The politeness principle including its maxims is one kind of the strategies.

Cooperative Principle (CP)

The Cooperative Principle (CP) is proposed by H. P. Grice. Grice expressed CP to suggest that in conversational interaction people work on the assumption that a certain set of rules is in operation, unless they receive indications to the contrary (Thomas, 1995, p.62). When speakers violate any of the maxims lead the addressee or hearer to make what Grice calls implicature. Those maxims will be explained as follows.

1. Maxim of Quantity

In this maxim we must (a) Make the contribution as informative as is required for the current purpose of the exchange, (b) Do not make our contribution more informative than is required (Leech, 1983, p.8). Those rules mean that the number of utterances used to deliver message must be informative as what is required and does not more or less than it; so that, the information does not boring or disappointing.

2. Maxim of Quality

There are two rules in this maxim, they are: (a) Do not say what you believe to be false and (b) Do not say that for which you lack adequate evidence (Leech, 1983, p.8). The meaning of these rules is clear that the delivered message must be truthful and does not lack suitable evidence.

3. Maxim of Relation

In this maxim, the rule is being relevant (Leech, 1983, p. 8). The meaning of “relevant” is the connection between what the speaker says and the addressee hears is related each other.

4. Maxim of Manner

The rules are: (a) Avoid obscurity of expression, (b) Avoid ambiguity, (c) Be brief (avoid unnecessary prolixity), and (d) Be orderly (Leech, 1983, p.8). It means utterance that is conveyed must be clear. There are two kinds of clarity, clear text and clear message. Clear text is constructed by syntax and phonology of the language. Then, the clear message is when the sense of illocutionary goal conveyed is understandable.

The cooperative principle and the politeness principle have a close relationship because they study about the use of language in communication using a set of principles or maxims to manage it. Besides, the politeness principle appears to argue the cooperative principle. The politeness principle says that not all people are being cooperative in a conversation to be polite.

Maxim Violation

According to Grice (1975) in Khosravizadeh & Sadehvandi (2011, p.1), a violation takes place when speakers intentionally refrain to apply certain maxims in their conversation to cause misunderstanding on their participants' part or to achieve some other purposes.

Grice (1975, p.45) in Tupan & Natalia (2008, p.68) gives the criteria of violation of maxims used as distinguished guidelines. Here are the guidelines:

1. Maxim of Quantity Violation:
 - a. If the speaker does circumlocution or not to the point
 - b. If the speaker is uninformative
 - c. If the speaker talks too short
 - d. If the speaker talks too much
 - e. If the speaker repeats certain words
2. Maxim of Quality Violation:
 - a. If the speaker lies or says something that is believed to be false
 - b. If the speaker does irony or makes ironic and sarcastic statement
 - c. If the speaker denies something
 - d. If the speaker distorts information.
3. Maxim of Relation Violation
 - a. If the speaker makes the conversation unmatched with the topic
 - b. If the speaker changes conversation topic abruptly
 - c. If the speaker avoids talking about something
 - d. If the speaker hides something or hides a fact
 - e. If the speaker does the wrong causality
4. Maxim of Manner Violation
 - a. If the speaker uses ambiguous language
 - b. If the speaker exaggerates thing
 - c. If the speaker uses slang in front of people who do not understand it.
 - d. If the speaker's voice is not loud enough.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The word research comes from the verb researching which means investigate or examine. Whereas, the term methodology is derived from the word *metodos* and *logos*.

Metodos means: way to go to achieve a goal, whereas *logos* means: science (Arikunto, 1990, p.16), so methodology means a science that discuss about the ways of achieving a truth. Based on the understanding above, the methodology is a way to search for truths that can be justified scientifically.

The approach for studying Dodit Mulyanto's utterances in Stand Up Comedy Indonesia is a descriptive qualitative method. Because, a qualitative approach is a research procedure that produces the descriptive data in the form of written words. The data sources in this study are the utterances of Dodit Mulyanto in Stand Up Comedy Indonesia Kompas TV season 4 by downloading from YouTube site. Furthermore, the researcher felt that the appropriate triangulation to be used in this paper is methodological triangulation. Methodological triangulation refers to the need of different instruments in gaining the data. In this case, the researcher conducted observation and transcript analysis

DISCUSSION

The data were the scripts of Dodit Mulyanto in Stand Up Comedy Indonesia Kompas TV season 4 below which analyzed by violating cooperative principles of conversation in detail. This research discovered that all types of maxims were violated and they were shown in percentage in the following table.

The percentage overview of violation maxims in Dodit Mulyanto's Stand Up Comedy Indonesia Kompas TV season 4.

No.	Types of Violation Maxims	Frequency	$X = \frac{F}{N} \times 100\%$
1.	Quantity	12	24,5%
2.	Quality	13	26,5%
3.	Relation	22	44,9%
4.	Manner	2	4,1%

	Total	49	100 %
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Table above shows that there were 49 utterances violation of maxim which were used in Dodit Mulyanto’s Stand Up Comedy Indonesia Kompas TV season 4. First, there were 12 utterances (24,5%) violation maxim of quantity. Violation maxim of quantity makes the speaker always repeat the same words and does circumlocution or not to the point. Second, there were 13 utterances (26.5%) violation maxim of quality. Dodit Mulyanto violated maxim of quality because it tend to make ironic and sarcastic statement and he said something that he believes to be false. Third, there were 22 utterances (44,9%) violation maxim of relation. Within the four violation maxims; violation maxim of relation was the most dominant in scripts Dodit Mulyanto’s Stand Up Comedy Indonesia Kompas TV season 4. Violation maxim of relation makes the speakers always to speak which is relevant. It means that there is a connection between what the speaker says and the addressee hears is related each other. Intentionally, Dodit Mulyanto in Stand Up Comedy Indonesia Kompas TV season 4 delivered too much message, which isunmatched with the topic or changed conversation topic abruptly or did the wrong causality, than is required to raise humor. Therefore, it violated the maxim of relation.

After maxim of relation, the most maxim which is used by Dodit Mulyanto is maxim of quality. Here, Dodit Mulyanto used some jokes that are believed to be false. In addition, Dodit also did irony or said sarcastic statements. Dodit Mulyanto often denied something and distorted information. All those effort are done in order to rise humor which violated maxim of quality up to 13 utterances (26,5%) from 49 utterance which he done.

The third maxim which is often Dodit Mulyanto used to perform is maxim of quantity. He did violated maxim of quantity up to 12 utterances (24,5%). He makes the contribution much of uninformative information as is required for the current purpose of the exchange. He also too much gave information. What he has done is violated maxim of quantity.

The last, those were 2 utterances (4,1%) violation of maxim of manner. It showed that violation of maxim of manner was the lowest number in scripts Dodit Mulyanto in Stand Up Comedy Indonesia Kompas TV season 4. Dodit Mulyanto seldom violated the maxim of

manner because it tends to use ambiguous or violates the utterances that have obscurity. Here were some examples of dialogues which violated each maxim.

After discussing about the maxim violation done by Dodit Mulyanto, here are some of the finding examples about the violation of politeness principle and cooperative principle and discussion and the using of maxims violation done by Dodit in order to rise humor.

1. Violation of Maxim of Quantity

Example 1:

Kentongan itu ada artinya, kalo dipukul sekali "tuk" "tuk" "tuk" sedang terjadi peristiwa pembunuhan. Ya, serius di desa tu seperti itu. Kemudian kalo ada bunyi dua kali "tuk tuk" "tuk tuk" sedang terjadi pencurian, kemudian kalo dipukul bunyinya gini (memukul seperti penjual mie ayam) maaf kentongannya dibajak.[Penonton tertawa dan tepuk tangan]. (P.3 L.3-7).

Translation

Kentongan has a variety of meanings, if it is hit once "tuk" "tuk" "tuk". it means there is a murder. Yes, seriously. That what happen in the village. Then, if it is hit twice "tuktuk" "tuktuk" it means the event of theft, then if it is hit like this (knocking such as chicken noodle seller) sorry, the *kentongan* has been hijacked [the audiences laugh and applause].

Analysis

This sentence was violated maxim of quantity, the researcher found an unnecessary sentence in the last of the paragraph, the sentence is: "then if it is hit like this (such as chicken noodle seller) sorry, the *kentongan* has been hijacked", this information is not required by the audience, but Dodit adds this in order to raise humor.

Example 2:

Saya makan itu table manner, peralatannya harus lengkap ada sendok, garpu, silet[Penonton tertawa] (P.2 L.2-3).

Translation

I used to eat with table manner, the equipment must be complete: spoon, fork, and blade [the audiences laugh].

Analysis

This second sentence violated maxim of quantity, the word “blade” in the last of the sentence should not be mentioned or may be replaced with the word “knife”, because a blade is not included in the table manner equipment or not used as tableware, but this kind of violation has raises humor among the audience successfully. The context of his speech is that Dodit want to explain about his breakfast. As the Javanese family that embrace European culture the breakfast in his family conducted in table manner, but in fact he has mistaken in mentioning the table manner stuffs.

2. Violation of Maxim of Quality

Example 1:

Saya itu dilahirkan istimewa, saya dilahirkan secara otodidak, [Penonton tertawa] saya lahir bidannya baru datang, jadi saya keluar sendiri [Penonton tertawa]. (P.3 L.1-2).

Translation

I was born specially, I was born autodidactly [the audiences laugh],and when I was born the midwife came late, so I go out alone [the audience laugh].

Analysis

According to Dodit, his born was very special, even he can go out from his mother’s womb by himself. This utterance violated maxim of Quality, because he said something that he believe to be false. Moreover, no body belief that the baby could go out by himself without any helping from nurse.

Example 2:

Saat saya pertama kali stand up, saya tu sangat takut menatap mata penonton, saking takutnya saya menatap mata saya sendiri[penonton tertawa] (P.3 L.1-2).

Translation

When I performed stand up for the first time, I was so scared to look at the audience's eyes, because of fear I looked at my own eyes [the audience laugh].

Analysis

The second sentence has violated maxim of Quality, it is proved with the last sentence: "because of fear I looked at my own eyes". As we know that looking at our own eyes is something impossible. In this case, Dodit told the audience something that believed to be false. This was happened when Dodit's perform his second speech and told his experiences during the first performance, he said that he was nervous and feared to look at the audience's eyes.

3. Violation of Maxim of Relation

Example 1:

Kalo pacaran sama pemain biola tu enak, bisa main titanic-titanican –musiknya langsung pakai biola-..... tapi pacar saya biar dipeluk orang lain, lha gimana saya bermain –kalau saya harus meluk pacar saya-? [Penonton tertawa] (P.5 L.1-7).

Translation

It is good to go out with a violinist, we can play like in the titanic scene -The music is immediately from the violin-..... but someone will embrace my girlfriend, so how can I play-If I embrace my girlfriend-? [the audience laugh] (P.5 L.1-7).

Analysis

This sentence violated maxim of relation, it is proved with the first sentence "It is good to go out with a violinist, we can play like in the titanic scene" has no relation to the last sentence "but someone will embrace my girlfriend, so how can I play?" Firstly Dodit was proud to be a violinist because he can play like in the titanic best scene -when Leonardo De Caprio hugs his girl from behind- and accompanied by his own live music, but in the last he realized that he cannot embrace his girlfriend if he must play violin.

Example 2:

Saya ndak boleh ngejar ngejar layangan sama bapak saya, saya tu bolehnya ngejar ngejar kamu... [Penonton tertawa] I love u! [Penonton tertawa] (P.1 L.3-4).

Translation

My father does not let me chase a kite, I was only allowed to chase you...[the audiences laugh] I love you! [the audiences laugh].

Analysis

This sentence violated maxim of relation, it is approved with the first sentence: “My father do not let me chase a kite” which has no relation with the second sentence: “I was only allowed to chase you... I love you”. In this case, the audience was thinking that Dodit’s father didn’t allow him to chase a kite because he afraid Dodit will be dirty, tired and looks plebeian. But in fact, Dodit answered it because he only allowed to chase a beautiful woman. If the sentence is changed like: My father does not let me chase a kite, because he afraid I will be tired. The sentence doesn’t rise humor effect. The context here is that Dodit is trying to be a romantic man like a classic European man who really adhere women by using his own words to flirt the girl.

4. Violation of Maxim of Manner

Example 1:

*Tau kan Presiden kita sukanya baris-berbaris? Piyekabare? [penonoton tertawa]
Iseh penak jamanku tho? [penonoton tertawa] #akurapopo (P.1 L.2-4)*

Translation

Do you know our former president who loves marching? How are you? [the audiences laugh] Is my decade still the best? [the audiences laugh] #I am okay.

Analysis

This sentence made some audience do not understand about who is the president that being told by Dodit. Hence, this sentence violated maxim of manner. This sentence was found after Dodit singing the mars of general election, after singing he explained that the song was created by the president at that time. Because the president was a former general of armed forces so the song beat was very fast like a marching soldiers, furthermore he tried to ask the audience who the president was by giving a code sentence.

Example 2:

.....koruptor jahat! (P.7 L.4)

Translation

.....the corruptors are criminals!

Analysis

In the last of his speech, Dodit said the sentence above without any reason and without any foreword and makes the audience confused. At the end, the audience laugh at this ambiguity. Because this sentence is unclear, so it has violated maxim of manner. The context is when Dodit delivers a speech that he was confused with the condition of this nation, then he plays a fast rhythm by his violin and in the last he said the sentence, of course the audiences amazed with his ambiguity.

CONCLUSION

After conducting research and analyzing the research problems about cooperative principle, it is concluded that Dodit Mulyanto violates all of the four maxims of cooperative principle: maxim of Quantity, maxim of quality, maxim of relation, and maxim of manner. There was found twelve data on the maxim of quantity violation, whereas the maxim of quality violated in thirteen data, maxim of relation is the most frequent maxim to be violated, it is proved by the research finding that it was violated twenty two times. Hence, the fewest violation occurred on the maxim of manner which only occurred two times.

Dodit has violated maxims of cooperative principle in various ways in order to raise humor of the audience. Maxim of quantity has violated by Dodit Mulyanto by adding an unnecessary sentence to his information and those unnecessary additional information succeeds to raise humor. Dodit violated maxim of quality by telling lies and saying something that is believed to be false by the audience. Whereas maxim of relation violated by Dodit by making the speech which is unmatched with the topic or his own statement before. Moreover, Dodit violated maxim of manner by using ambiguous language. In addition, Dodit is doing all of these violations only to raise humor among the audience and not for the other purpose.

The violation of cooperative principle is not always become a bad thing in communication. On the contrary, it and may be applied in daily life in order to make a joke, to perform stand up comedy or public speaking, to make teaching method more interesting for

the teacher or lecturer and of course, it may be researched again in depth in order to enrich the knowledge about humor based on linguistic approach.

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